

Twin Transition for The Timber Industry

Deliverable 7.7 Data and Ethics Management Plan

5G-TIMBER | Work Package 7, Task 7.3

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05/09/2022	Henri Schasmin (TalTech)	DRP sends the draft for the named reviewers (2 or 3 persons: WP leader unless DRP & deliverable consumer(s)). Includes both Word version and PDF version. PDF version is needed to check e.g., broken cross-references, fonts, layout, etc.
16/09/2022	Stefania Fortino (VTT) and Colin Keogh (ICP)	Reviewers send their reviews back to DRP for revision.
23/09/2022	Henri Schasmin (TalTech)	DRP addresses the comments in one week.
23/09/2022	Stefania Fortino (VTT) and Colin Keogh (ICP)	Reviewers approves the deliverable and send it coordinator/technical manager
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Glossary of terms and abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G	5 th Generation
AR	Augmented Reality
CA	Consortium Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DRP	Deliverable Responsible Person
DT	Digital Twin
DOA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GeA	General Assembly
PMB	Project Management Board
QARM	Quality Assurance & Risk Manager
UCs	Use-Cases
WVC	Wood Value Chain

1. Executive Summary

This document provides the reader with guidelines on 5G-TIMBER project activities related to two major dimensions: A) legal, ethics and gender issues and B) data management issues.

The first purpose of this document is to guide the project members on the principles and procedures to be followed regarding both these dimensions. The second aim of this document is to highlight the risks associated to both these dimensions measures to mitigate them.

This document sets out common methods and procedures for the project research process in data management, ethics, legal, gender and legal area that should be applied by all members of the consortium.

This document defines the guidelines and recommendations underlying the research ethics protocol in accordance with the current legal and ethical framework. In this respect, 5G-TIMBER consortium partners commit to adhere to fundamental ethical principles and relevant national, European Union and international legislation, including:

1. the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union,
2. the General Data Protection Regulation,
3. the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, and
4. the European Convention on Human Rights.

In relation to the ethics issues, the respective ethics protocols included in this document materialise this commitment. This also sets out the responsibilities of the partner and describes the procedures and methodologies that will ensure the ethical basis of 5G-TIMBER research, test cases and field trials.

Throughout the project, the 5G-TIMBER partners will adhere to the Research Ethics Protocol in their work. Implementation of the Research Ethics Protocol will be monitored and refined including an update on the review procedures. These will be documented in two follow-up deliverables:

1. D7.8 "Initial data management report" due on M12,
2. D7.9 "Final data management report" due on M36.

The compliance of 5G-TIMBER research activities and field trials with ethical standards, guidelines and legislation will also be strengthened and ensured through the activities of the Ethics Panel of experts.

The intended audience of the 5G-TIMBER Data and Ethics Management Plan consists of the members of the 5G-TIMBER consortium and the Project Officer.

2. Introduction

This document is D7.7 “Data and ethics management plan” and results from the work carried out in T7.3 “Data Management, Ethics and Ethical Compliance” of WP7. This document was prepared by considering the assessment of potential data management, ethics, gender and legal concerns relating to the project’s activities as known at this stage of the project.

The implementation of the project's ethical principles will take into account:

1. in case of involvement of human beings, how and when research will involve them;
2. potential legal and ethics concerns on individuals’ recruitment;
3. processing and protection of personal data according to EU and national data protection law, including the General Data Protection Regulation;
4. processing and protection of project other data (research information and business/ trade secrets);
5. gender perspectives.

The aim of this document is to identify, describe and apply the procedures and methodology to:

1. ensure that 5G-TIMBER research activities and field trials (use cases) are both ethically and legally sound;
2. secure that data from research participants is stored according to EU and national regulations to ensure their privacy;
3. provide due consideration to gender balance issues.

The aim of this document is to fulfil the following main objectives:

1. to provide specific guidelines to ensure adherence of the project’s partners with ethics requirements imposed by the Grant Agreement;
2. to provide recommendations to ensure that the processing of personal data for research purposes by the project’s partners comply with the General Data Protection Regulation and its national implementation laws;
3. to provide an information sheet and an informed consent form template and instructions on how to comply with it to the project’s partners for the purpose of communicating about the project with third parties and involve third parties in events;

4. to provide specific baseline document for the Ethics Panel to review and approve the ethics requirements of the project;
5. to provide more specific recommendations on how to give due considerations in terms of gender balance in relation to the project's management and participation as well as in the proposed research methodologies, and how to monitor these considerations;
6. to provide more specific recommendations for the establishment and activity procedures of an Ethics Panel of experts consisting of experts on ethics, privacy, gender and legal issues.

2.1 Mapping 5G-TIMBER Outputs

This section maps the components (elements) described in the 5G-TIMBER's Description of Action (DoA)/Grant Agreement (GA), i.e., the description of the deliverable and task description in the DoA/GA, against the chapters included in this deliverable and the justification of the work conducted in the project. See Table 1.

Table 1 Adherence to 5G-TIMBER's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-TIMBER GA Element	5G-TIMBER GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D7.7 Data and Ethics Management Plan	The task behind D7.7 is T7.3 (Data Management, Ethics and Ethical Compliance) and is about innovation, ethics and data management of the project (developed Use Cases). TalTech dedicated DPO will be leading the efforts in ensuring appropriate compliances.	Chapter 3-6, and appendices I to IX	Data and Ethics Management are provided for the project.
TASKS			
T7.3 Data Management, Ethics and Ethical	Related to all core WPs, this task will facilitate and monitor the innovation and data related exploitation and protection activities of the project, as	Chapter 3-6, and appendices I to IX	Data Management and Ethics Compliance is

Compliance	well as ethics, gender and GDPR related issues of the project. Main tasks of the innovation, ethics and data manager will be: Supporting the consortium partners in setting up their individual exploitation plans; Monitoring the technical, human, and financial risks; Drafting the data management and ethical compliance deliverable.		required for the project.
Section 1.2.4	The initial version of the DMP will be conducted by month M4 (D7.7), and will evolve during the lifetime of the project in order to present the status of the project's reflections on data management (M12, D7.8); the final version will be delivered in M36 (D7.9).	Chapter 6 and Appendix IX	Data Management and Ethics Compliance is required for the project.
Section 1.2.5	A Data Management Plan (D7.7-D7.9) will make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR), including all procedures to archive and collect data, including adopted standards and interfaces, and make them available based on their nature. DMP defines usage, management, maintenance, back-up procedures of data repository.	Chapter 6 and Appendix IX	Data Management and Ethics Compliance is required for the project.

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Following the introduction in this Chapter 2, Chapter 3 presents an overview of the research legal background. Chapter 4 provides a description of the research and ethics background. This is complemented by a description of the research ethics policy and protocols followed in the project in Chapter 5. Next, Chapter 6 presents the data management principles and procedures followed in the project. Finally, Chapter 7 concludes this deliverable.

In addition, 9 appendices are included: I) human participation related activities, II) health and safety regulations, III) ethics checklist form, IV) ethics controlling report, V) information sheet example template, VI) informed

consent form example template, VII) anonymous informed consent template, VIII) non-anonymous informed consent template, and IX) data management report template.

Note that data and ethics issues will be monitored continuously and reported in the subsequent deliverables (D7.8 due on M12 and D7.9 due on M36).

2.3 Other project outputs

This section describes the interdependencies with the other project tasks and activities.

a) Interdependencies between the task(s) of this deliverable and the other WPs:

Task T7.3 documented in this deliverable D7.7 (which will be updated in D7.8 and D7.9) is transversal to the project and thus provides background information, procedures, and guidelines to all the other WPs in terms of innovation, ethics and data management of the project and ensures appropriate compliance. T7.3 will facilitate and monitor the innovation and data related exploitation and protection activities of the project, as well as ethics, gender and GDPR related issues of the project. T7.3 will thus not only provide input to all other WPs but will also collect input for monitoring and reporting purposes.

b) Interdependencies between the task(s) of this deliverable and the other similar WP Tasks:

WP7 comprises 3 main tasks, of which one is further divided into 2 sub-tasks:

- T7.1 Project Coordination, Technical & Innovation Management
- T7.2 Quality Assurance, Financial, Legal and Risk Management, which is further divided into:
 - T7.2.1: Implementation of quality assurance procedures
 - T7.2.2: Supervision and coordination of legal, financial and administrative issues
- T7.3 Data Management, Ethics and Ethical Compliance

Since T7.3 deals with transversal issues of data management, ethics and ethical compliance, interaction and synchronization within WP7 will take place with T7.1 (overseeing the overall project execution) and

T7.2 (overseeing quality assurance and risk management in T7.2.1 and legal, financial and administrative issues in T7.2.2).

Table 2 provides a list of the other deliverables that produce inputs to this deliverable or consume outputs from this deliverable.

Table 2 List of the other deliverables that produce inputs to this deliverable or consume outputs from this deliverable.

5G-TIMBER GA Element	Contribution and Value of linkage
<i>Input from D1.1 to D1.9 for D7.7 to D7.9</i>	These deliverables will provide details of the work carried out in WP1, including but not limited to the UCs definitions and KPIs definitions. T7.3 will keep assessing potential data and ethics issues that might arise from WP1, making sure WP1 follows the guidelines and procedures provided in D7.7 to D7.9.
<i>Input from D2.1 to D2.14 for D7.7 to D7.9</i>	These 14 deliverables will document the details of the work carried out in WP2 in terms of the technological innovations for wood industry pilots and ecosystem supply chain and their federation, integration and orchestration. T7.3 will keep assessing potential data and ethics issues that might arise from WP2, making sure WP2 follows the guidelines and procedures provided in D7.7 to D7.9.
<i>Input from D3.1 to D3.12 for D7.7 to D7.9</i>	These 12 deliverables will document the details of the work carried out in WP3 in terms of system level integration and operational readiness for executing the use case pilots. So far, one potential ethics issue (human participation in four different trials) has been identified in WP3 (see TABLE 8 in Appendix I), but T7.3 will keep assessing potential data and ethics issues that might arise from WP3, making sure WP3 follows the guidelines and procedures provided in D7.7 to D7.9.
<i>Input from D4.1 to D4.8 for D7.7 to D7.9</i>	The 8 deliverables from WP4 will document the deployment of 5G-TIMBER applications into demonstration sites. Several ethics issues (human participation) have been identified (see

	<p>Appendix I) and T7.3 will keep assessing potential data and ethics issues that might arise from WP3, making sure WP3 follows the guidelines and procedures provided in D7.7 to D7.9.</p>
<p><i>Input from D5.1 to D5.8 for D7.7 to D7.9</i></p>	<p>These deliverables will provide details about the status and progress of WP4 in terms of commercialisation, innovation management and standardisation activities. T7.3 will keep assessing potential data and ethics issues that might arise from WP2, making sure WP2 follows the guidelines and procedures provided in D7.7 to D7.9.</p>
<p><i>Input from D6.1 to D6.5 for D7.7 to D7.9</i></p>	<p>These 5 deliverables will document the work carried out in WP6 in terms of dissemination, communication and scale-up for maximizing the project impact. So far, one potential ethics issue (human participation in four different trials) has been identified in WP3 (see TABLE 8 in Appendix I), and T7.3 will keep assessing potential data and ethics issues that might arise from WP3, making sure WP3 follows the guidelines and procedures provided in D7.7 to D7.9.</p>
<p><i>Output from D7.7 for all other deliverables</i></p>	<p>D7.7 is transversal to the project and will provide background information, procedures, and guidelines about innovation, ethics and data management to all the other WPs to ensure all partners are aware of and follow them.</p>

3. Research Legal Background

3.1 EU Research Legal Background

Main Regulation of Research and Development (Horizon Europe). REGULATION (EU) No 2018/0224 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 07.06.2018 *Establishing Horizon Europe - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027)* [1].

General and specific objectives. According to Article 3 *Programme objectives*, the Programme's general objective is to deliver scientific, economic and societal impact from the Union's investments in research and innovation so as to strengthen the scientific and technological bases of the Union and foster its competitiveness, including in its industry, deliver on the Union strategic priorities, and contribute to tackling global challenges, including the Sustainable Development Goals.

Gender equality. According to Article 6 *Implementation and forms of EU funding*, the Programme shall ensure the effective promotion of gender equality and the gender dimension in research and innovation content. Particular attention shall be paid to ensuring gender balance, subject to the situation in the field of research and innovation concerned, in evaluation panels and in bodies such as expert groups.

Main ethical principles. The research and innovation activities carried out in 5G-TIMBER project shall comply with ethical principles and relevant national, European Union and international legislation, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols. Particular attention shall be paid to:

1. the right to the physical and mental integrity of a person;
2. the right to non-discrimination;
3. the right to privacy;
4. the right to the protection of personal data;
5. the principle of proportionality;
6. the need to ensure high levels of human health protection.

Main Regulation of Electronic Communications. Directive 2018/1972 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 *Establishing the European Electronic Communications Code* [2].

This Directive establishes a harmonised framework for the regulation of electronic communications networks, electronic communications services,

associated facilities and associated services, and certain aspects of terminal equipment. It lays down tasks of national regulatory authorities and, where applicable, of other competent authorities, and establishes a set of procedures to ensure the harmonised application of the regulatory framework throughout the Union.

The aims of this Directive are to:

1. implement an internal market in electronic communications networks and services that results in the deployment and take-up of very high-capacity networks, sustainable competition, interoperability of electronic communications services, accessibility, security of networks and services and end-user benefits; and
2. ensure the provision throughout the Union of good quality, affordable, publicly available services through effective competition and choice, to deal with circumstances in which the needs of end-users, including those with disabilities in order to access the services on an equal basis with others, are not satisfactorily met by the market and to lay down the necessary end-user rights.

Project 5G-TIMBER takes into account main regulations of Electronic Communications in Europe. Special attention is paid to the countries where trials will be conducted and of which project partners should be aware of.

Main national research legal background. Main national research legal background is described in the following table (Table 3).

Table 3 Main national research legal background

	Partner	Country	National regulation of research and development activities	National regulation of electronic communications
1	Athonet Italy	Italy	Personal Data Protection Code (Legislative Decree No. 196 of 30 June 2003).	Personal Data Protection Code (Legislative Decree No. 196 of 30 June 2003), in particular in Articles 121 to 132-quater.
2	Jotne	Norway	Norwegian R&D is regulated by the Research Council of Norway (NFR), these are the guidelines and general terms and	Act relating to electronic communications (The Electronic Communications Act) - Lovdata

			conditions for R&D projects. Link generelle-vilkar-01012021-engelsk-oppdaterert-februar-21.pdf (forskningsradet.no)	
3	Acceleran	Belgium	Decision of 12 May 2017 made by the Flemish government for a program to support enterprises in research and development with a knowledge intensive character in Flanders; Decision of 12 May 2017 made by the Flemish government for a program to support enterprises in development and innovation in Flanders; and Decision of 23 February 2018 made by the Flemish government regulating the co-financing of research and development in public contracts.	The Act of 21 December 2021 transposing the European Electronic Communications Code and amending various provisions on electronic communications.
4	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland	Finland	The Data Protection Act (1050/2018); other special legislation may be applicable on a case-by-case basis for instance the Act on the Secondary Use of Social and Health Data (552/2019), which is applicable to the secondary use of social and health data.	Act on Electronic Communications Services (917/2014).

5	Crowdhelix	Ireland	https://assets.gov.ie/137380/bd9942c5-ac53-40b8-8765-3decc5650ca9.pdf	https://www.lawreform.ie/fileupload/RevisedActs/WithAnnotations/HTML/EN_ACT_2002_0020.htm#:~:text=This%20Revised%20Act%20is%20an,and%20consolidation%20of%20statute%20law
6	Polimi	Italy	http://www.ricercainternazionale.miur.it/evidenza/normativa-programmi-internazionali.aspx	Legislative Decree No. 259 of 1 August 2003 – Electronic Communications Code (the Electronic Communications Code) https://www.agcom.it/en
7	Inlecom Systems	Ireland	https://assets.gov.ie/137380/bd9942c5-ac53-40b8-8765-3decc5650ca9.pdf	https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2002/act/20/enacted/en/html

The project partners will specify their research legal background. The requirements of the national legislation will be specified during the further activities of the project.

3.2 Legal aspects of Privacy, including General Data Protection Regulation and National Data Protection Regulations

3.2.1 General Data Protection Regulation

General provisions of personal data processing and protection

In the 5G-TIMBER project perspective, it is important to emphasize that the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) applies to any organisations based in the EU and organisations, wherever they are located that are selling goods and services in the European Union or processing the personal data of individuals in the European Union.

The GDPR is designed to give individuals control over their personal data and is an important effort for protecting individual rights and freedoms. According to GDPR the protection of natural persons in relation to the processing of personal data is a fundamental right [3]. The principles of, and rules on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of their personal data should, whatever their nationality or residence, respect their fundamental rights and freedoms, in particular their right to the protection of personal data.

The processing of personal data should be designed to serve mankind. The right to the protection of personal data is not an absolute right; it must be considered in relation to its function in society and be balanced against other fundamental rights, in accordance with the principle of proportionality. In terms of the 5G-TIMBER project and GDPR principles, it is important to emphasize, that the economic and social integration resulting from the functioning of the internal market has led to a substantial increase in cross-border flows of personal data.

Main Principles of Data Processing and Protection. With respect to data processing, protection and privacy, the 5G-TIMBER project must be implemented in a way that safeguards the fundamental rights for natural persons. This implies compliance with the principles of:

1. lawfulness, fairness and transparency;
2. purpose limitation;
3. data minimisation;
4. accuracy;
5. storage limitation;
6. integrity and confidentiality;
7. accountability.

Data Protection Impact Assessment. The Project team shall, in certain cases, prior to the processing, carry out an assessment of the impact of the envisaged processing operations on the protection of personal data (GDPR Article 35 *Data Protection Impact Assessment*).

Data Protection Impact Assessment is required:

1. if using new technologies;
2. taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing;
3. is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.

A Data Protection Impact Assessment shall in particular be required in the case of:

1. a systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons which is based on automated processing, including profiling, and on which decisions are based that produce legal effects

- concerning the natural person or similarly significantly affect the natural person;
2. processing on a large scale of special categories of data referred to in Article 9(1), or of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10; or
 3. a systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale.

Data Protection Officer. The controller and the processor designate a Data Protection Officer (DPO) in any case where:

1. the processing is carried out by a public authority or body;
2. the core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing operations which, by virtue of their nature, their scope and/or their purposes, require regular and systematic monitoring of data subjects on a large scale; or
3. the core activities of the controller or the processor consist of processing on a large scale of special categories of data pursuant to Article 9 and personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10.

3.2.2 National Data Protection Regulations

3.2.2.1 Data Protection Regulation in Estonia

Personal Data Processing for scientific purpose. Personal data may be processed without the consent of the data subject for the needs of scientific research, in particular in a pseudonymised format or a format which provides equivalent level of protection. Prior to transmission of personal data for processing for the needs of scientific research, personal data shall be replaced by pseudonymised data or data in a format which provides equivalent level of data protection.

De-pseudonymisation or any other method by which the data not enabling identification of persons are changed again into the data which enable identification of persons are only permitted for the needs of additional scientific research. Processors of personal data shall designate a person identified by name who has access to the information allowing pseudonymisation.

Processing of data concerning any data subjects for the needs of scientific research without the consent of the data subject in a format which enables identification of the data subject is permitted only in the case the following conditions are met [4]:

1. the purposes of data processing can no longer be achieved after removal of the data enabling identification or it would be unreasonably difficult to achieve these purposes;
2. there is overriding public interest for it in the estimation of the persons conducting scientific research;
3. the scope of obligations of the data subject is not changed based on the processed personal data or the rights of the data subject are not excessively damaged in any other manner.

Restriction of the data subject's rights. Where personal data are processed for the purpose of scientific research, the controller or processor may restrict the rights of data subjects provided for in Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 of GDPR insofar as the exercise of these rights is likely to make the achievement of the objectives of the scientific research impossible or impedes it to a significant extent.

The national data protection regulations. The national data protection regulations of the project partners are described in the following table (Table 4).

Table 4 The national data protection regulations of the project partners

	Partner	Country	Personal Data Protection Regulation	Link to Personal Data Protection Regulation
1	Athonet Italy	Italy	Personal Data Protection Code (Legislative Decree No. 196 of 30 June 2003)	https://www.garanteprivacy.it/documents/10160/0/Codice+in+materia+di+protezione+dei+dati+personali+%28Testo+coordinato%29
2	Jotne	Norway	The Personal Data Act	Regulations Datatilsynet
3	InnovaWood	Belgium	Act on the Protection of Natural Persons with Regard to the Processing of Personal Data	https://www.dataguidance.com/jurisdiction/belgium#:~:text=Summary&text=Summary%3A%20Belgium%20implemented%20the%20GDPR,to%202013%20years%20of%20age.

				https://www.dataguidance.com/notes/belgium-data-protection-overview https://www.linklaters.com/en/insights/data-protected/data-protected---belgium ; https://www.dataguidance.com/notes/belgium-data-protection-overview Data Protected Belgium Insights Linklaters ;
4	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland	Finland	The Data Protection Act (1050/2018); The Act on the Protection of Privacy in Working Life (759/2004)	To specify
5	CrowdHelix	Ireland	Data Protection Act	https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2018/act/7/enacted/en/html
6	Polimi	Italy	Personal Data Protection Regulation	https://www.garanteprivacy.it/web/garante-privacy-en/the-italian-data-protection-authority-who-we-are
7	Inlecom Systems	Ireland	Data Protection Act	https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2018/act/7/enacted/en/html
8	THALES AIS		Data Protection Act	https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bdsg_2018/ https://dejure.org/gesetze/DSGVO
9	Accelleran	Belgium	The Act of 30 July 2018 on the Protection of Natural Persons with Regard to the Processing of Personal Data.	

The project partners will specify their national data protection regulations. 5G-TIMBER project partners will take into account the specificities of their national data protection regulations. The corresponding supervision is carried out by the partner's Data Protection Officer.

3.3 Main Legal Concerns

The main legal concerns of 5G-TIMBER project are related to fundamental research, technological, ethical and data protection legislation. European Union and national legislation determine the main frameworks within which the project will be implemented.

Not all legal issues may be unambiguous during 5G-TIMBER project implementation. 5G-TIMBER participating partners may have different interpretations of certain legal aspects. It is therefore important that 5G-TIMBER project partners address the legal framework as consistently as possible. Ethics, legal and data protection process protocols and guidelines help to create a common understanding of compliance. This guideline on ethics and legal monitoring also helps to establish compliance.

It is also important to define use-cases and trials as accurately as possible, factoring in the specific EU and national legal requirements.

In the case of 5G-TIMBER research activities, the main subject is to carry it out in accordance with the rules laid down. Meeting the requirements for European Horizon projects is an important aspect here.

The conduct of this 5G-TIMBER research must comply with the requirements set out in the project conditions, which in turn are based on the requirements of Horizon Europe. Non-compliance with these requirements can significantly affect the implementation and results of the project.

There are some risks associated with research, technological solutions and data protection:

1. misinterpretation of the legal aspects of research may result in financial or reputational damage;
2. technological requirements of 5G-TIMBER are also important to follow. Non-compliance with technological conditions affects the implementation and results of the project;
3. compliance with data processing and protection requirements is an important aspect of conducting 5G-TIMBER research. Non-compliance with data processing and protection requirements may lead to project failure and damage both financially and reputationally.

4 Research Ethics Background

4.1 EU Research Ethics Background in Horizon Europe projects

4.1.1 Ethics Declarations and Conventions

In the context of Horizon Europe projects, the research and innovation activities shall comply with [1]:

1. ethical principles;
2. relevant national legislation;
3. relevant Union and international legislation, including:
 - 3.1 the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and
 - 3.2 the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocol.

Particular attention shall be paid to:

1. the principle of proportionality;
2. the rights of human participants and of the vulnerable population that may be implicated in the use cases;
3. the right to privacy and to the protection of personal data;
4. the right to non-discrimination and;
5. the need to ensure high levels of human health protection.

5G-TIMBER consortium partners confirm and commit to adhere to:

1. fundamental ethics principles;
2. relevant national, European Union and international legislation, including:
 - 2.1 the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union;
 - 2.2 the Convention of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data;
 - 2.3 especially General Data Protection Regulation.

The abovementioned principles and legislation will be followed when addressing the project's ethical questions and issues.

Project members participating in 5G-TIMBER must carry out their research activities in accordance with Article 8 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (protection of personal data).

It is important to note that ethics and European values go beyond data protection and privacy.

The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [7] implements a structure of six value areas, three of which require specific scrutiny in 5G-TIMBER project:

1. **dignity**, notably individuals' right to be secure in their physical and mental integrity.
2. **freedoms**, comprising the rights to data protection and privacy, but also intellectual freedoms (education, expression, thought, religion and information) and social freedoms (assembly and property);
3. **equality**, including non-discrimination and rights of minorities and of societally more vulnerable parties.

4.1.2 European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

5G-TIMBER consortium partners are also bound by the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity which includes the following research integrity principles [5]:

1. **reliability** – in ensuring the quality of research, reflected in the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources;
2. **honesty** – in developing, undertaking, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair, full and unbiased way;
3. **respect** – for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment;
4. **accountability** – for the research from idea to publication, for its management and organisation, for training, supervision and mentoring, and for its wider impacts.

5G-TIMBER researchers' personal responsibility is to carry out their research based on good research practice following the context described in the Code of Conduct in Research integrity covering:

1. research environment;
2. training, supervision and mentoring;
3. research procedures;
4. safeguards;
5. data practices and management;
6. collaborative working;
7. publication and dissemination;
8. reviewing, evaluating and editing.

The 5G-TIMBER researcher observes the following safeguards:

1. handles research subjects, be they human, animal, cultural, biological, environmental or physical, with respect and care, and in accordance with legal and ethical provisions;
2. has due regard for the health, safety and welfare of the community, of collaborators and others connected with their research;
3. research protocols take account of, and are sensitive to, relevant differences in age, gender, culture, religion, ethnic origin and social class;
4. recognises and manage potential harms and risks relating to their research.

The researcher must examine the research plans potential ethical issues and take steps to correct them and must do so prior to contacting any participants. The proposed research plan, and how it puts into practice, must survive ethical evaluation in advance. If an ethical problem exists, the researcher must modify the research plan. Only when the research plan can stand up to ethical challenges can the investigator start or proceed to the next phase.

The researcher must address in their research with human participants the issues of:

1. explicit and informed consent;
2. confidentiality;
3. safety;
4. deception;
5. debriefing;
6. security and
7. diversity.

The task of researcher is to think the abovementioned issues through in order to find out whether the participants will experience and perhaps react negatively on any of these issues.

It is important to emphasize that all partners of the consortium are fully committed and agree to collaborate for the fulfilment of their above-mentioned ethical responsibilities.

4.2 Gender perspective

4.2.1 Introduction

5G-TIMBER aims at embedding gender equality at each stage of the project. The European Parliament has supported and called for measures to improve the position of women.

There are three objectives that underpin the strategy on gender equality in Horizon Europe projects:

1. **Fostering gender balance in research teams** – in order to close the gaps in the participation of women;
2. **Ensuring gender balance in decision-making** – in order to reach the target of 40% of the under-represented sex in panels and groups and of 50% in advisory groups;
3. **Integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation content** – helps improve the scientific quality and societal relevance of the produced knowledge, technology and/or innovation.

The European Commission's Gender Roadmap Short guide defines a Gender Equality Plan as a set of actions aiming at:

1. Conducting impact assessment of procedures and practices to identify gender bias;
2. Identifying and implementing innovative strategies to correct any bias;
3. Setting targets and monitoring progress via indicators.

4.2.2 Implementation

According to the Horizon Europe requirements the beneficiaries must:

1. take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action;
2. aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level.

Considerations for gender balance in research teams include:

1. Balanced representation of the genders in research and innovation activities to the possible extent as well as in management structures and research teams;
2. "Collective intelligence" meaning that no gender dominates over the other;

3. Balanced representation in decision-making.

The current male-female ratio of the project. The current male-female ratio of the project is described in the following table (Table 5).

Table 5 The current male-female ratio of the project

	Partner	Country	Male	Female
1	Athonet Italy	Italy	Researchers: 4 Other staff: 4	Researchers: 1 Other staff: 2
2	Jotne	Norway	4 Other staff: 9	1 Other staff: 5
3	InnovaWood	Belgium	2	2
4	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland	Finland	Researchers: 5	Researchers: 1 Other staff: 1
5	Crowdhelix	Ireland	4	1
6	Accelleran	Belgium	Researchers: 3-4	0
7	Harmet	Estonia	Other staff: 9	Other staff: 3
8	Polimi	Italy	Researchers: 4	Other staff: 2
9	Inlecom Systems	Ireland	Researchers: 3	Researchers: 2 Other staff: 2
10	TIETO FI	Finland	Researchers: 2	0
11	TIETO SE	Sweden	Researchers: 2	0
12	Octavic	Romania	Researchers: 2	0
13	THALES AIS	Germany	Other staff: 5	0
14	Hekotek	Estonia	Other staff: 4	Other staff: 2
15	TalTech	Estonia	Researchers: 4 Other staff: 1	Researchers: 2 Other staff: 1

The project partners will specify their male-female ratio of the project.

Situation on measures

It is a fact that the topics addressed in 5G-TIMBER see more male than female employees, whether in academia or industry. Nevertheless, the

project already has a number of female participants, including in decision-making roles.

Project 5G-TIMBER is committed to creating and sustaining a work environment that:

1. promotes equal opportunities across gender and;
2. clearly prohibits discrimination.

Project 5G-TIMBER supports equal career opportunities by:

1. making sure that working hour arrangements will not disproportionately disadvantage those with caring responsibilities;
2. having the Project Management Office regularly monitor issues related to gender, ranging from hiring to career opportunities and retention of staff.

Project consortium and members will systematically analyse the relevance of sex/gender regarding the different expectations males and females may have towards 5G-TIMBER innovation.

The innovative outcome and the project itself will consider the gender dimension and will cater for the needs, motivations and differences between females and males where applicable.

As part of the project, sex/gender analysis will be addressed with respect to:

1. **The requirements analysis:** A balanced participation of male and female professionals will allow gender analyses to be incorporated into the early user requirement definition. As per the recommendations of the European Institute for Gender Equality, we will sex-disaggregate the data to identify possible different expectations regarding the GUI interfaces, features, functionality, etc. based on sex/gender.
2. **All steps of the technology enablers development:** The GUI interface designs and ML algorithms (e.g. parameters) will be consulted with both males and females at different ages, and posterior alpha and beta versions will be trialled by both males and females. Gender differences of perception, understanding, cognition and reaction will be carefully considered in relation to the system's development.
3. **The trials and evaluation of the results thereof:** the possible usage of the innovation shall benefit males and females equally (as direct or indirect end-users). Behavioural specificities will be considered during the field trials and diversity and gender balance within end-user test

groups will be ensured. The gender level of participation within the 5G-TIMBER activities will be monitored. Equal opportunities and equal treatment between men and women will be guaranteed.

4. **5G-TIMBER will ensure that during all its phases**, and as much as possible equal gender participation will be maintained. This concerns both research, laboratory experiments and development phases, as well as the field-scale testing with the different use-cases. Gender dimension will be one of the field scale and other test/evaluations participants' characteristics that will be tracked in order to derive relevant conclusions, if possible and applicable.
5. **The dissemination, communication and exploitation activities:** gender will be considered and the gender-equality dimension promoted in the training, promotional and educational materials, in the target groups of the community building and outreach activities, as well as in the business models. This is essential for contributing to the education of the current professional and next generation of scientists, technologist and others needed in the EU to maximise its creativity and innovation potential. The dissemination and communication activities will promote the participation of female presenters in project workshops and in large-scale dissemination activities such as European and International Seminars and Conferences. Project achievements of female researchers and WP Leaders will be promoted via the project's website and social media acting as role models.

In addition, 5G-TIMBER will be vigilant in addressing the impact of the research in gender balance, although the proposed activities do not at this point imply to impact this dimension.

4.3 Ethical Aspects of Privacy

5G-TIMBER researchers accordingly follow in addition to national and EU legislation:

1. the appropriate ethics guidelines and rules for data handling and storage and;
2. informed consent procedures and participant recruitment criteria at their institution.

The general objective of this Ethics policy and special guidelines is to ensure to compliance with ethics requirements. The essential requirements relate to data processing and privacy during the 5G-TIMBER project.

The right to data protection is a fundamental right (according to the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union). Any 5G-TIMBER use case where personal data is processed will need to adhere to applicable data protection law.

It is important to notify that any ethics evaluation requires an explication of the normative framework against which the anticipated innovation is to be assessed.

In the research process, the central ethical concern is compliance with the fundamental right to data protection and privacy.

In relation to the abovementioned principles, the 5G-TIMBER project does not foresee any implication/ infringement of private communications or other aspect of family life. However, it is important to keep this condition in mind throughout the life of the project.

4.4 Research background

4.4.1 Research objectives

Research objectives. Main research objectives are to validate the latest 5G industrial private network features and standards specifications for Wood Value Chain (WVC) under realistic conditions. This includes field trials of data-driven material, production and installation flows, implicating manufacturing in the wood sector: machinery and wood house elements manufacturing, construction and renovation towards green buildings, wood waste valorisation, as well as telecom SME industries spanning 3 representative European regions (Norway, Estonia, Finland).

Locations of the research. Locations of the research are:

1. Tallinn University of Technology (TalTech), Ehitajate Tee 5, 19086 Tallinn, Estonia
2. Crowdhelix Limited (CHX), Trinity House 7 Georges Quay, Cork T12nax0, Ireland
3. Athonet Srl (Athonet Srl), Padriciano 99 Area Science Park, Trieste 34149, Italy. Operations Headquarter, Via Ca' Del Luogo 8, Bolzano Vicentino 36050, Italy.
4. Inlecom Commercial Pathways Company limited by Guarantee (ICP), Core B Block 71 The Plaza Park West, Dublin 12 D12WDN2, Ireland
5. Jotne EPM Technology As (Jotne), Grenseveien 107, Oslo 0663, Norway

6. Harmet Ou (Harmet), Puusepa Tee 4, Kumna 76614, Estonia. Assembly of the modules takes place in Talvitie 32, 96190, Rovaniemi, Finland.
7. Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus Vtt Oy (VTT), Tekniikantie 21, Espoo 02150, Finland
8. Politecnico Di Milano (Polimi), Piazza Leonardo Da Vinci 32, Milano 20133, Italy. Campus la Masa Sud, via la Masa 1,20156, Milano, Italy.
9. Innovawood Asbl (Innovawood), Rue Du Luxembourg 66, Bruxelles 1000, Belgium
10. Hekotek As (Hekotek As), Porguvalja Tee 9 Lehmja Rae Vald, Harjumaa 75301, Estonia
11. Tieto Finland Oy (Tieto-Fi), Keilalahdentie 2 4, Espoo 02150, Finland
12. Tieto Sweden Ab (Tieto), Fjarde Bassangvagen 15, Stockholm 115 83, Sweden
13. Octavic Pts Srl (Oct), Strada Colinelor 70a, Oradea 410156, Romania
14. Thales Dis France Sas (Thales DIS), 6 Rue De La Verrerie, Meudon 92190, France
15. Thales Dis Ais Deutschland Gmbh (Thales AIS), Werinherstr. 81, Munchen 81541, Germany
16. Accelleran (ACC), Quellinstraat 49, Antwerp 2018, Belgium. Kievitplein 20 bus 4.2, 2018 Antwerp, Belgium.

The purpose of the lab trials is to pre-test the functionalities and the readiness of the UCs in restricted closed and controlled environment (WP3) and allow the fine-tuning of the technological enablers (WP2) which will be integrated and validated in the field trials (WP4). Details about the work that will be carried out in lab trials will be clarified in later deliverables.

Lab trials. Lab trials will take place in testbeds of:

1. Testbed sites of TalTech in Tallinn (Estonia)
2. VTT in Espoo (Finland)
3. POLIMI in Milan (Italy) and Tieto in Stockholm (Sweden)
4. THALES in La Ciotat (France)

Taltech testbeds comprises 3 setups:

- i) Taltech 5G-SA private network supports mmWave band enterprise solutions from Ericsson (cloud-native architecture, 5G-SA core and RAN, HDS command center SW).

- ii) Wooden material laboratories for physical and chemical properties testing.
- iii) Wooden construction test buildings – (a) 3-store zero energy dormitory building renovated with external wooden elements with embedded SHM sensors; (b) civil engineering campus building fully composed of multilayer wooden elements, laboratories for construction elements properties testing and aging.

UC1.2, UC1.3, UC2.1, UC2.2, UC3.1, and UC3.2 will be validated in lab trials in TalTech's Testbeds.

VTT wood-modelling testbed (Espoo, Finland) includes 3 setups:

- i) Facilities for numerical modelling: Workstations and high-performance computational clusters at VTT for FEM modelling. Abaqus code and other codes in VTT ProperTune toolset will provide software frameworks incorporating scripts and subroutines needed for the modelling. Furthermore, VTT Modelling Factory is a virtual working space to be used in connection with LCA software such as SULCA. In addition,
- ii) Facilities for predictive maintenance: VTT has laboratory facilities for the development and testing of digitalized, e.g. open-source predictive maintenance tools and services.
- iii) Facilities for experimental tests: Scratch tests device and X-ray computed tomography equipment.

Digital Twin testbed (POLIMI) and Enhanced Reality Lab (Tieto, Sweden/Finland). In-lab prototyping, and validation of the proposed solutions and approaches will be carried out at Polimi taking advantage of the available laboratory facilities. With respect to DT approaches for manufacturing processes and systems, the Manufacturing Lab will be made available, providing both hardware (CNC machines), software (process planning and optimization) and computational (HPC cluster) resources. For AR application, the resources and facilities of the Haptics and Virtual Prototyping laboratory facilities will be utilized for UC1.2, UC2.2, and UC3.1 initial testing and validation.

Tieto's Enhanced Reality Lab is to provide the human perspective to disruptive innovation and support novel ways of working and design thinking

methods for teams across multiple industries and dimensions of immersive experiences and their application in employee and customer experience.

THALES Testbed (La Ciotat, France). Thales will provide an AWS Ireland VPC (Virtual Private Cloud), a Trusted Key Manager (TKM). This platform will allow to generate secrets and credentials for Trust seeding, and manage credential life cycle. APIs will be Rest based and will be extended in the course of the project (WP2) with OPCUA to reach any end point supporting OPCUA, and LWM2M COAPs protocol to reach eSIM embedded in Thales connectivity modules used in 5G TIMBER Gateway. 5G TIMBER devices/equipment involved in cybersecurity will be provisioned and enrolled within this platform. The platform will be available as a Test bed for development phase (WP2) and will be extended up to field trials.

The purpose of the field trials is to demonstrate and validate both the interdisciplinary technologies and use cases of the vertical industries (i.e, sawmill machinery, wood-house factory, construction and renovation with wooden elements, valorisation of composite waste) so as to enable their commercial exploitation. Field trials will validate use cases in advanced WVC deployments in Northern Europe areas (Norway, Estonia, Finland) by characterising and optimising enabling technologies in field trials, to validate applicable standards and key target KPIs. During the project, each use case will deploy a layered testing practice to drive development, involving significant industry representative tests, verifications and validations.

Field trials (Use Cases):

1. Sawmill machinery manufacturer (Hekotek, Põrguvälja tee 9, Jüri, 75306 Harjumaa, Estonia)
2. Sawmills . At the time of writing, discussions are ongoing with two **candidate** sawmills:
 - a. AS Aegviidu Puit, Niinsoni tee 2, Aegviidu, 74501 Harju maakond
 - b. AS Viiratsi Saeveski: Vana-Võidu küla, Viljandi vald 70108 Viljandimaa
3. Woodhouse manufacturing site (Harmet, Puusepa tee 4, Kumna, 76614 Harjumaa, Estonia)
4. "Pilot A: tailored made construction of wood house in Norway" (exact location TBD, Norway)
5. "Pilot B: renovation of an apartment house in Estonia" (exact location TBD, Estonia)

6. "Pilot C": temporary modular house installation in Rovaniemi, Finland (exact location TBD)

Details about the activities that will be carried out at the pilot sites will be clarified in later deliverables.

At the time of writing, the initial definition of the scope of the use cases in T1.1/D1.1 is ongoing in parallel with T7.3/D7.7. The detailed information about the actual data that will be produced and consumed by the use cases will be collected in live Excel files in the 5G-TIMBER online environment ([example](#)) and will be documented in subsequent D7.8 and D7.9 reports. This will also be supported by the individual data management reports of which a template is provided in Appendix IX.

4.4.2 Main Ethics Concerns

5G-TIMBER will consider these principles:

1. During the 5G-TIMBER project, data related to the technology and processes will be processed.
2. It is not planned to regularly process data directly related to the individuals during the 5G-TIMBER project.
3. Appropriate security measures shall be taken in the event of the processing of personal data.
4. In the case of human participation, the relevant ethical procedures are followed.

Tallinn University of Technology is the lead partner responsible for the delivery of the aforementioned requirements under the advisory of the Ethics Panel (EP), described in the next section, under the supervision of Mr. Henri Schasmin (TalTech).

Artificial Intelligence. Supplementary ethical issue could be the respect of principles and key requirements outlined in the "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence", should the 5G-TIMBER project consider AI supported operational infrastructure.

To be considered trustworthy, the development of such infrastructure must be:

1. Lawful – respecting all applicable laws and regulations.
2. Ethical – respecting ethical principles and values.
3. Robust – both from a technical perspective while taking into account its social environment.

Main technologies. The 5G-TIMBER project will use edge-computing, 5G, and AI technologies to enable small and medium-sized manufacturing industries to make use of efficiency-improving tools.

The 5G-TIMBER project will use the wood value chain (WVC) in the Use Cases.

Key technologies that will be deployed include:

1. open standards for data production and exchange;
2. data analytics at the edge;
3. precise indoor localization;
4. Digital Twins;
5. augmented reality and industrial IoT.

Potential emerging issues. No severe issues with AI technologies, personal data or human involvement are foreseen.

4.4.3 Compliance with health and safety (H&S) procedures and other ethics issues

Some use cases in field trials will be performed with humans participating in the 5G-TIMBER trial testing and at public and official locations. These humans involved are researchers, employees and volunteers.

The 5G-TIMBER consortium partners must ensure and train the researchers and the external research participants to follow the appropriate Health and Safety (H&S) procedures on departmental/institutional but also on regional/national level. The researchers are staff of consortium partners.

In 5G-TIMBER project, it is important to comply with the following provisions of EU directives:

1. Safety and health of workers at work (*Framework Directive 89/331/EC*).
2. The use of work equipment (*Directive 2009/104/EC*).
3. The minimum health and safety requirements regarding the exposure of workers to the risks arising from physical agents (electromagnetic fields) (*Directive 2013/35/EU*). Specifically, provisions for relevant risk assessments, as per the precautionary principle, when certain exposure conditions are met (*Directive 2013/35/EU*).

If required by law, permits must be obtained from the relevant authorities for testing. The physical risks arising from safety issues must also be taken into account. The provisional overview of the respective H&S guidelines/legislation/protocols for the 5G-TIMBER test sites is provided in D7.7 Annex II.

This overview will be stored in the 5G-TIMBER MS Teams online collaboration platform in folder WP7/T7.3, will remain as a live document, and will be annexed in D7.8 “Initial data management report” due on M12 and D7.9 “Final data management report” due on M36.

5G-TIMBER partners are responsible for:

1. each pilot site, testbed and Use Case owners to follow the provisions of the aforementioned directives;
2. identifying and following with any other H&S institutional protocols and different safety provisions that may be applicable;
3. informing the Ethics Panel about the respective protocols.

5. 5G-TIMBER Research Ethics Policy and Protocols

The purpose of the ethics tasks of the 5G-TIMBER project is to ensure that the innovations accompanying the project are in line with European ethics and moral values. This is done by applying theory of Value Sensitive Design. Theory of Value Sensitive Design is an approach that aims to integrate a broad range of human and moral values into the design of information technology. Value Sensitive Design means that a normative framework is defined and the designers of the system – in this case the 5G-TIMBER project – integrate this framework into their work.

5.1 Scope

The Horizon Europe requirements provide that “the beneficiaries must carry out the action in compliance with: (a) ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity) and (b) applicable international, EU and national law. The beneficiaries must ensure that the activities under the action have an exclusive focus on civil applications.

In addition, the beneficiaries must respect the fundamental principle of research integrity – as set out, for instance, in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and means that beneficiaries must ensure that persons carrying out research tasks follow the good research practices and refrain from the research integrity violations described in this Code.

This chapter outlines the policy embedded in the ethics management guidelines for the 5G-TIMBER consortium on research ethics.

5.2 5G-TIMBER Ethics and Risk Management Safeguards

5.2.1 Ethics Management Safeguards

5G-TIMBER has established several safeguard mechanisms to ensure compliance with ethics principles. Ethics Management Safeguards are described below.

1. **Research Ethics Protocol.** The 5G-TIMBER’ Research Ethics Protocol (i.e. this chapter) has been defined for guiding project activities.
2. **Data Management and Ethics Leader.** The project Data Management & Ethics Leader, as well as the project DPO has been appointed.
3. **Data Protection Officer.** The project partners appoint their own internal DPO who will closely collaborate with the project’s DPO. The project

partner provides the name and contact details of its DPO. The list of DPO's will be updated by the project partners/ Ethic Panel members and remain a live document, stored in online collaboration platform in folder WP7/7.4.

- 4. Ethics Panel.** The Ethics Panel (EP) has been established. This panel is chaired by the project Data Management & Ethics Leader and includes advisors of the participating members (with experience and expertise related to ethics, privacy, and legal issues).

The EP is available for providing advice and shall monitor the compliance of the project activities with the 5G-TIMBER' Research Ethics Protocol.

- 5. Communication and contact information.** The following email address shall be used for internal use when seeking appropriate communication related to ethics issues: henri.schasmin@taltech.ee.
- 6. External expertise.** In case any specific issue should arise for the EP members provide insufficient expertise to deal with, an external expert will be invited to the Ethics Panel and will act as an independent reviewer and consultant.
- 7. Project Management Board.** The 5G-TIMBER' Project Management Board (PMB) has been established; it is composed of different manager roles that ensure the quality conduct of the research activities, as well as the protection of the rights of participants' rights protection.
- 8. Documents.** Two follow-up documents will update the progress made during the project:
 1. D7.8 "Initial data management report" due on M12;
 2. D7.9 "Final data management report" due on M36.
- 9. Ethics control and monitoring.** The Ethics Panel will be obliged to comply with the Ethics Policy of the project, the European and national/ regional regulations and practices and report back to the Project Management Board about the ethics compliance of the relevant activities as well as any issues that may arise respectively.

In addition, in regard to the use cases, a summary of each pilot site will be obtained and the information will become the **ethics profile** of each pilot site. This will be done by having the investigating partner responsible for conducting trials involving human participants filling in an **Ethics Controlling Report** and its respective EP member making sure that there is no missing information and/or ethical issues raised through the Ethics Checking Form.

Annex III provides the template for the Ethics Checking Form and Annex IV provides the relevant template for the Ethics Controlling Report.

5.2.2 Ethics and Legal Risks Identification and Mitigation Strategy

It is not possible to imagine a procedure, investigation or process that is without any risk. One of the most important factors in risk assessment is the prospective participant's perception of the significance of the risk. The life situation of the participant can significantly influence how the risk is perceived. The end point of the process is the consent a person gives to participate in a research project after considering all aspects of the process and asking all relevant questions.

All relevant information will be provided to participants. This means that the 5G-TIMBER project will be carefully explained.

The physical risks from safety issues are minimized thanks to H&S protocols and are expected to be at the same level as the average working people when they are busy, tired, stressed, etc.

Below is an initial risk identification and mitigation strategy. In accordance with the requirements of the DoA, the ethical risks associated with the project's data processing operations are presented, including an opinion on whether a data protection impact assessment should be carried out under Article 35 of the General Data Protection Regulation.

Preliminary ethics and legal risks identification and proposed mitigation strategy

1. Application of overarching Ethical and legal framework. All relevant legislation, regulation and ethical codes will be considered; they are defined how they are met in terms of processes, timing and responsibilities. 5G-TIMBER Ethics Panel will oversee the ethical concerns involved in the project and the ethics approval processes at project level. Annex III includes the information required to be addressed (Ethics Checklist) which partners might be required to obtain prior any testing takes place.

2. Transparency and consent of the Use Case participants. The informed consent administration ensures that the user accepts participation and is informed about the project and the Use Cases objectives. Written consent is obtained after participants are informed. Information provided is clear and

understandable about their roles (tasks and rights), research objectives and methods applied, duration of study and participation (if they differ), confidentiality, safety and risk related issues as well as the benefit for them and the project. These aspects are depicted in the informed consent form template (annexed in D7.7). Completed documents will be appended to D7.8 and D7.9 for reporting.

The basic parts of the 5G-TIMBER informed consent will include:

1. The objective of the study, its duration and methodology;
2. Possible risks, discomforts and side-effects;
3. Privacy and data protection procedures;
4. The possibility to decline the offer and to withdraw at any point of the process (and without consequences)
5. Information about the data controllers, processors and data manipulation in general;
6. Identification of data controllers and processors;
7. Contact person.

3. Privacy and data protection. Only anonymised data will be processed and, therefore, no personal data will be processed in relation to specific user. The name will not be connected to other characteristics (e.g. age, gender, nationality, health and/or mobility profile). Anonymous data handling falls under the European and national legislation for the lawful processing of personal data.

To avoid risks related to the processing of personal data such as identity theft, discriminatory profiling or continuous surveillance, the principle of proportionality has to be respected. Data can be used only for the initial purpose for which they were collected.

Anonymisation or pseudonymisation is a way to prevent violations of privacy and data protection rules. Processing has to be limited to what is truly necessary and less intrusive means for realising the same end have to be considered.

5.3 Ethics Panel

Ethics experts will be involved in the 5G-TIMBER project research process as appropriate. The respective body of ethics experts will be formed according to the needs of the 5G-TIMBER project activities. The internal ethics body –

Ethics Panel – is formed on the basis of the 5G-TIMBER project members. The role of this Ethics Panel is to work together to address the internal ethical issues of the project as they arise.

The Ethics Panel:

1. will monitor ethics aspects related legal, gender and privacy issues in the 5G-TIMBER project;
2. will consult the 5G-TIMBER project consortium on the relevant potential impacts of the activities undertaken.

The Ethics Panel is necessary to ensure critical appraisal of the ethical, gender and legal issues arising from the activities of the project. The Ethics Panel acting as supervisor the ethical activities of the project and considering both European and national ethical and legal requirements.

It is especially important to evaluate the activities of the 5G-TIMBER project related to the involvement of human participants (i.e. surveys, questionnaires, testbeds and use cases) and thus the possible processing of personal data.

Special guidelines, including this material, will be developed to support the activities of the project members, ethics experts and Ethics Panel.

The Ethics Panel plans to participate in the most important project report meetings. Members of the Ethics Panel are free to organise supplementary meetings in accordance with legal and ethical issues that may arise during the implementation of the project (ad hoc meetings or task/issue specific meetings on a need to do basis).

Composition of the Ethics Panel. In 5G-TIMBER, the Ethics Panel consists of advisors (experts in data management, ethics, privacy, gender and law) of the participating members. The Ethics Panel is formed of the respective representatives of the participating members.

These members will be designated on the basis of proven expertise and qualification in the fields of data management, ethics, privacy and law. The selection of the members of the Ethics Panel shall be based on the following principles included in Table 6.

Table 6. Required expertise for members of the Ethics Panel

Legal requirements	Professional requirements	Competence requirements	Educational requirements
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Representative of the participating member with a valid contract (employment contract, etc.).	The performance of the duties has been related to research and development. Priority shall be given to persons that are also involved in test-beds and field testing activities.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Previous experience in technology projects. 2. Previous experience with project ethics. 3. Previous experience with legal and data protection issues. 	Higher education, at least a master's degree.
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Relevant consortium partners have suggested a qualified member to join the panel accompanied by a CV and approved first by the panel chair.

Ethics Panel members, their research activity with humans and required opinions/approvals are planned to be described in Table 7.

Table 7. Ethics Panel members, research activity with humans and required opinions/approvals

Partner	Ethics Panel Member	Research activity involving humans	Opinions/ approvals by ethics committees and /or competent authorities
TalTech	Henri Schasmin		
Harmet	Mari Emmus Rauno Loonurm		
Polimi	Marcello Uργο		
Inlecom Systems	Colin Keogh		

Table 7 will be continuously updated by the Ethic Panel members and remain a live document for reference, stored in the online collaboration platform in folder WP7/T7.4, and annexed in D7.8 on M12. The Chair of the Ethics Panel

should be notified in case a partner wishes to substitute its Ethics Panel member and approve accordingly.

5.4 Recruitment rules

When involving external research participants, their recruitment is guided by three main principles [6]:

1. Participation is voluntary and the participant may withdraw from research at any time;
2. Recruitment corresponds to the research question and methods; and
3. Participants will be selected in a non-discriminatory manner.

5.4.1 Recruitment Criteria

5.4.1.1 Participants Freedom

5G-TIMBER strictly follow “Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU” [7]; “European Charter for Researchers” [8] and “Ethics in Social Science and Humanities” [9] when human research is conducted. Details of the procedures and criteria for each relevant activity are made readily available to the 5G-TIMBER project external participants. The participant decides whether he/ she wants to participate in the activity or not.

5.4.1.2 Inclusion and Non-Discrimination

5G-TIMBER complies with relevant national and international regulations when use cases and test field/ test site activities involve humans.

Special attention is paid to compliance with DIRECTIVE 2006/54/EC of July 5, 2006 [10] on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and profession (reworded).

Article 14 and Protocol No. 12 of the European Convention on Human Rights, as well as the European Handbook on Non-Discrimination [11] issued by the EU Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA) – 2018 edition.

5.4.1.3 Research Integrity

Research integrity is based on good research practices. By ensuring a good research environment, greater trust in researchers is achieved and they are better engaged in the practical, ethical and intellectual challenges inherent in their research work.

Therefore, the basic principles of research integrity are important recruitment criteria for 5G-TIMBER (European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity [5]):

1. "reliability",
2. "integrity",
3. "respect",
4. "responsibility".

5.4.1.4 Vulnerable populations

Vulnerable populations are unlikely to participate in the research. Vulnerable users (e.g. homeless, drug and alcohol users and immigrants, etc.) will not be recruited to participate in pilot site use cases managed by the 5G-TIMBER consortium.

5.4.2 Recruitment Procedures

As a general rule, participants are identified and selected by use case leaders for inclusion in the research. They will recruit participants from their respective networks according to the profile specified for testing the 5G-TIMBER tools. Research participants are invited to participate according to their role in the organization that may be relevant to the activities of the 5G-TIMBER project.

The procedures listed in the following paragraphs are followed to respond to identified risks and obstacles.

5.4.2.1 Rights of Participants Procedures

According to the European Charter for Researchers, 5G-TIMBER is responsible for the rights, safety, well-being and interests (or dignity, integrity, rights and autonomy) of people involved in research, as well as for all communities involved in research, i.e. "to society at large, in terms of the contribution that scientific research can make to socially useful and valued development and change, but also from the point of view of avoiding possible misuse or unintended consequences" of research results" [8].

Thus, participation in the activities of the 5G-TIMBER project is completely voluntary; all participants can ask questions and receive comprehensible answers before making decisions about participation.

Informed Consent Forms and Information Sheets. Informed consent forms and information sheets will be provided to recruited participants. The consent process is developed and presented in D7.7 including appendices with various consent templates and information sheets attached. Actual filled documents will be appended to D7.8 and D7.9 for reporting purposes. However, the process of informed consent, whether for recruitment or testing, remains an integral part of the 5G-TIMBER ethics policy. These templates are reviewed and adjusted prior to any testing. They are also reviewed by the Ethics Panel.

Each trial site representative is responsible for the proper translation and adaptation of all relevant consent forms and their safe storage. Annex V (Information Sheet) and Annex VI (Informed Consent Form) provide examples of preliminary templates for cross-border trials.

Withdrawal. Participants also have the right to withdraw themselves and their personal data, as well as to stop participating in the study at any time. They are also reminded of their rights before participating. This information will be communicated to the participants by means of an information sheet. The consent form is signed twice, one signed copy is given to the participant.

Recognition of research results. 5G-TIMBER Pilot participants are informed that the main results and outcomes of the pilots will be shared with them and will be in an accessible format (e.g. odt, *.pdf, html, printed, braille, etc) if such a requirement arises.

Continuous support during testing. During testing, the testing and/or use case team members ensure that the participants are comfortable and not forced or fatigued. Questions are allowed during testing, at designated times. Participants should be informed of this possibility in advance. Contact details will be provided to the participant along with all information and contacts in case participants have any questions after testing is complete.

Compensation. All participants are strictly voluntary. Appropriate compensation mechanisms will be established for recruited participants. These mechanisms are approved by the Ethics Panel before being administered.

In cases where a repayment incentive is provided, applicants (research interviewees) should be informed of the payment status in disclaimer letters using the following terminology:

"If you participate in a face-to-face interview/trial/survey/test, you will receive a cash reward of €XX for your assistance with this research. This does not in any way affect your entitlement to compensation."

In general, the application of compensation as an incentive payment is avoided.

5G-TIMBER Privacy, Transparency, Confidentiality, Risk Assessment and Participant Acknowledgment Policy for 5G-TIMBER Research. Each subject and person responsible for use cases should explain the following to recruited participants:

1. General scope of 5G-TIMBER and a brief reference to its objectives.
2. Scope and brief description of the test/use case and corresponding research.
3. The value of participation. The supervisor will explain the benefits of participation to the project, i.e. how it contributes to the research being carried out in the project and why the participant should consider joining this research as a research participant (benefits to both the participant and the public in general).
4. Risk analysis. The biggest risk identified is related to unrealistic hopes and expectations for personal benefits from 5G-TIMBER project results. This is countered by the explicit provision of information on the limitations of such personal benefits and harms.

Test and use case plans ensure that participants are not harmed and the pre-testing activity provides the necessary reassurance.

None of the tasks related to the use case (neither tests nor field pilots) are expected to have (side) impacts on the participant's physical or mental integrity or health, other than those occurring in their daily activities.

As different user groups are addressed (including potential disabled people and various stakeholders such as operators, service providers, etc.), all sites internally review use case plans and arrive at a decision on the inherent risks of all potentially addressed users and groups.

Harm is not foreseeable in any way, but the partner in charge of the use case ensures that they explain the situation to the recruited participants, especially in relation to safety and security issues, i.e. if harm can occur during the incidents, experiments and what are the measures taken to prevent it and reduce such chances.

All necessary precautions are also taken in case of safety related issues (i.e. caution information and usage scenarios).

In all cases, the test sites will comply with the internal and/ or national safety regulations applicable to their areas.

5.4.2.2 No Discrimination Procedures

The prevention of discriminatory outcomes before the research activity (i.e. during the selection of participants) and after (i.e. during the dissemination and use phase) is supported by the enforcement of all necessary measures to protect groups and individuals from stigmatization due to gender, race, religion, sexual orientation, political beliefs, ethnicity and other social characteristics.

Through inclusive, clear, accessible and transparent procedures, 5G-TIMBER strives to recruit

- 1) women (targeting as close to a 1:1 ratio of women to men as possible) and
- 2) people from diverse backgrounds.

Any exclusionary practices, marginalization, research devaluation and stereotyping are considered unacceptable.

5.4.2.3 Ensuring Good Understanding of Procedures

In order to ensure that participants understand the information correctly and effectively, 5G-TIMBER partners must follow certain requirements for each project activity involving people.

1. Submission of customized protocols, including procedural details. In addition, the selected criteria are made readily available to participants to ensure the required specificity of the information sheet [3].
2. Ensuring that potential participants are fully informed and do not feel pressured, coerced, threatened or stressed by researchers to give consent.

For this purpose, according to the request of GDPR, different procedures are implemented to ensure that the freedom of the participants is respected.

3. Prevention of deception. Under no circumstances will researchers mislead potential participants into research that is expected to cause physical pain or severe emotional distress.

Researchers will explain to participants any deceptions that are an integral part of the design and conduct of the experiment as early as possible, preferably at the end of their participation, but no later than the end of data collection, and allow participants to retract their deceptions.

5G-TIMBER pilots are deception-free and the user is informed at all stages of the evaluation about the objectives and procedures related to the test fields and use cases and how their data is handled, processed and stored.

When the service functionality is simulated, they are informed but asked to act and react as if the situation were real.

4. Debriefing. Researchers will ensure that participants have prompt access to relevant information about the nature, results, and conclusions of the research and will take reasonable steps to correct any participant misconceptions of which researchers are aware.

The debriefing must be documented and signed by both parties.

Summaries and copies of research reports will be presented in a format accessible to research participants (e.g, larger font size, use of simple text with photos, oral communication, etc.) and communicated through dissemination channels (e.g, website, social media, etc.).

5. Presentation of all information (verbal, written or recorded) in a language and manner fully understood by the participants. This provides the unambiguity required by [3].
6. Clarification of the voluntary nature of participation and right to refuse participation. Participants have the right to withdraw participation or data at any time without consequences. This ensures that participants' freedom to join or not is respected.
7. Clarification of the aims, methods and effects of the research, the nature of participation and the resulting benefits, risks or inconveniences. This guarantees the participant's right to be informed of possible consequences (including possible risks).
8. Indication of the application of procedures in case of unexpected or incidental findings (in particular, whether the participants have the right to know about such findings or not).
9. Providing participants with researcher contact information so that they can contact the project consortium for information and to decide whether they wish to join.

In case of anonymous involvement (i.e. no personal data is collected during the activity), the informed consent template is attached to this document as Annex VII: Anonymous Informed Consent Template.

In addition, the Non-Anonymous Informed Consent Template contains a template for the collection of personal data, which is presented in Annex VIII.

The informed consent form consists of two parts:

1. the Information Sheet and
2. the Consent Form.

Both parts are distributed among the participants before the activity begins. The informed Consent Form, duly signed by the person or her/his legal representative, will be kept safely and in a file by the organizer of the activity throughout the duration of the project, notifying the ethics committee via the corresponding e-mail address.

The specificity of each activity requires the preparation of an ad hoc customized information sheet and consent form. Therefore, the templates mentioned above must be adapted to the specific activity.

The forms and templates listed in the appendices of this document will be translated by the corresponding partner into the language of the host country.

6. Data Management

This chapter provides an overview of the guiding principles which will be used in the management of research data during and after the 5G-TIMBER project. It also defines the concepts and objectives of data collection and details the data collection, protection and disclosure procedures that will be implemented to successfully complete this project task.

As the 5G-TIMBER project is still in its early stages, this overview is preliminary and will be updated as necessary during subsequent iterations of the Data Management Plan.

The data that is collected, created and disseminated in each 5G-TIMBER WPs is defined and grouped by documentation, management, reporting, research and tests files.

Data types can include narrative text, numbers, images, audio files, video files, internal/external reports, KPIs, statistics, figures, questionnaires, checklists, user input/feedback, etc. Such aggregated data is stored in a dedicated and protected data repository; to be used as an input for project work in the future and to provide a basis for the analysis of results, scientific publications and usage activities.

The data collected throughout the 5G-TIMBER project is continuously evaluated:

1. compliance with ethics and General Data Protection Regulation;
2. eligibility for distribution and publication; and
3. suitability for the protection and use of intellectual property.

6.1 Personal Data Processing and Protection

6.1.1 Main personal data processing requirements, constraints and controls

Main personal data processing requirements, constraints and controls according to General Data Protection Regulation:

1. Individuals give explicit consent to the collection of data. "Consent by default" does not apply.

The organization seeking consent will also provide clear information about how this data is used, how long it is kept and how it is shared with third parties. Individuals may withdraw consent at any time without restriction.

If the data is used for processing outside of the initial consent, additional permissions must be requested from the individual.

2. The DPO is appointed in the cases provided for in the Article 35.
3. Organisations shall conduct an internal data processing impact assessment to understand personal data risk exposures. GDPR Art. 35 defines what are the cases when a DPIA is mandatory, and all partners should monitor if a formal DPIA is required by the nature of research activities.

If needed, partners can consult the project DPO and the EP for guidance.

4. If the processing would result in a high risk in the absence of measures taken by the organisation to mitigate the risk, the supervisory authority prior to processing shall be consulted.
5. Data protection shall be by design and by default, requiring data protection mechanisms to be embedded into products and services from the earliest stage of development, and the adoption of strictest privacy settings without any manual input from the end user.
6. Individuals rights shall be guaranteed:
 - a. Individuals shall have easier access to their data, enabling them to review what data is stored about them and how it is processed, who it is shared with, along with the ability to migrate that data between service providers without restriction.
 - b. Individuals shall have the "right to be forgotten", also known as "right to erasure", so that there is no legitimate reason for an organization to refuse the request of individuals to definitely remove their personal data when they ask for it to no longer be retained.
7. Profiling and automated decision making shall ensure the profiling data subjects' rights.
8. Any data breach shall be notified to the Data Protection Authority.
9. Personal data processed for any purpose or purposes shall not be kept for longer than is necessary for that purpose or those purposes.
10. Personal data protection: No personal data will be centrally stored, without anonymization or pseudonymisation as needed. In case of pseudonymisation, only the persons designated in the DMP will have access to the relation between participant's code and identity, in order to administer the tests. More on Data Management policy in detail will be discussed in D7.8 'Initial Data Management Report 'and D7.9 'Final Data Management Report'.

All those requirements are included in 5G-TIMBER Research Ethics Protocol and illustrated in the following sub-sections.

6.1.2 General Data Protection Regulation Compliance

The activities of the 5G-TIMBER project are related to privacy and data protection issues, collecting data from the project participants from EU countries.

The following categories of data are obtained or created within the project:

1. Project administrative and management data;
2. Project events and workshops data;
3. Education and training data;
4. Data collected from public sources (document database, codes of practices, government guidance, relevant legislation database, results of ethical horizon scanning);
5. Open-Source data collected from publicly available sources;
6. Quantitative and qualitative evaluation data from deployment and pilot lab testing;
7. 5G-TIMBER publications to partners and official authorities.
8. Dissemination related data.

Annex IX - 5G-TIMBER Data Management Overview per WP, provides a list of all datasets currently expected to be generated in the 5G-TIMBER project and their planned accessibility. This list will be developed as the 5G-TIMBER project progresses.

6.1.3 5G-TIMBER Personal Data Processing and Protection Rules

In general, only anonymized or aggregated data (completely separated from human identification and profiling) related to participation in the research process of the project and data generated or processed during the course of the project (e.g. during the pilots) will be processed.

If the processing of personal data may be necessary for specific reasons, the interested 5G-TIMBER partner remains responsible for the data collected during its research and must comply with European and national privacy and data protection regulations.

6.1.3.1 Consent Procedures and Forms

Explicit consent to personal data collection have to be provided by each potential participant, prior to their involvement in the 5-TIMBER project activities.

The GDPR defines consent of the data subject as any freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her.

Moreover, the Recital 32 "Conditions for Consent" in states that consent shall be given by a clear affirmative act establishing a freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous indication of the data subject's agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her, such as by a written statement, including by electronic means, or an oral statement.

Consent is not just a simple form or document to be filled and signed by the individual; it is first and foremost a process that involves the individual and the entity entitled to collect and manage data.

The most important aspect in the informed consent process is to unambiguously ensure that individual is properly informed in a comprehensive language and that individual effectively understands the research activity, how data are used and the risks to be harmed.

In this perspective, the process of informing project activities participants and ensuring their understanding shall be carried out by considering the following conditions in order to:

1. Ensure the specificity of consent, an ad-hoc tailored consent form shall be distributed to all individuals, prior their involvement in project activities that collect personal data.

In case of processing of "special category of personal data", those participating will have a separate consent form, with a paragraph adding more details on the purpose of the processing, the duration of the processing, the plans for storing and sharing that data and their rights of access, correction and erasure.

This data will be destroyed as soon as possible after the specific objectives to which the data relates are achieved;

2. Reduce the risk of ambiguity, misunderstanding and incomprehension, the consent form to be filled and signed shall be translated into participant's mother tongue;
3. Reduce the risk of access to the information, the consent form shall be provided to participants either in hard copy or online;

4. Be compliant with the “Privacy by Default” principle, as well as to respect the freedom of individuals, consent form shall not provide “default checked answers” that can dissuade to express particular opinions and trigger to “pure acceptance” behaviour of participants;
5. Respect the freedom of the individuals, informing phase and understanding phase shall be carried out by ensuring necessary time to take the right decision and consequently sign or not the consent form.

For complying with specificity requirements, a consent form shall be produced and customised for each activity. Thus, a template to be customised for the specific project activity is included in this document as Annex VIII: Non-Anonymous Informed Consent Template.

The informed consent form is composed of two parts:

1. the Information Sheet and
2. the Consent Form.

Both of them shall be distributed among participants prior the activity will start.

The informed consent form, duly signed by the individual or his/her legal representative, shall be kept secure and on file for the whole duration of the 5G-TIMBER project by the activity organizer, who shall notify it to the Ethics Panel using the relative email address.

Informed Consent is needed to be obtained both for personal data and audio/video records management. In this respect, there should also be acknowledgement on video/sound recording sessions and screen capturing facilities (if applicable). If this is applicable, written consent is obtained before the session starts with a dedicated type of consent form. If the participant does not agree to this, the recording will not take place.

6.1.3.2 Designation of the Partner DPO

If personal data is processed by a consortium partner, this partner informs the project Ethics Panel. In addition, the partner involved in the collection and/or processing of personal data appoints a DPO in accordance with the GDPR well in advance of the start of the collection/ processing and communicates this to the project Ethics Panel.

6.1.3.3 Declaration on Compliance and/ or Authorisation

In case of collecting and/ or processing personal data, the partner shall check if a declaration on compliance and/or authorisation is required under national law for collecting and processing personal data.

If yes, copies of the declaration on compliance and/or authorisation shall be kept on file for the whole duration of the project, by the partner.

If no, declaration on compliance or authorisation shall be required under the applicable national law, a statement from the designated Data Protection Officer that all personal data collection and processing will be carried out according to EU and national legislation shall be kept on file for the whole duration of the project, by the partner.

In both cases, the above documentation shall be submitted to the project Ethics Panel to be included in deliverable D7.8 and D7.9.

Both actions shall be carried out well before the collection/ processing will take place.

6.1.3.4 Data Protection by Default and by Design

Partners are requested to adhere to what is defined in Art. 5 of the GDPR, so that personal data shall be:

1. processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject ('lawfulness, fairness and transparency');
2. collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes.

Further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with Article 89(1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes ('purpose limitation');

3. adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed ('data minimisation');
4. accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date.

Every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay ('accuracy');

5. kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed.

The personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) subject to implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by this Regulation in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject ('storage limitation');

6. processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures ('integrity and confidentiality');

6.1.3.5 Individuals Rights

The GDPR is designed to provide EU citizens with more control over their own personal data. Therefore, appropriate procedures and state-of-the-art technologies shall be applied for data collection, storage, protection, retention, destruction, and confirmation.

The details on those procedures are defined in the D7.7 and supplemented in the Initial Data Management Report and the Final Data Management Report.

6.1.3.6 Automated Individual Decision-making, Including Profiling

As stated by Art. 22 of the GDPR, the data subject shall have the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal impacts concerning that person or correspondingly altogether affects the person in question.

Automated processing and profiling are authorised if the decision is:

1. Necessary for entering into, or performance of, a contract between the data subject and a data controller;
2. Authorised by Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject, and which also lays down suitable measures to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests; or
3. Based on the data subject's explicit consent.

In case of automated processing and profiling, the data controller shall implement suitable measures to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interests, at least the right to obtain human intervention on the part of the controller, to express his or her point of view and to contest the decision.

6.2 Dissemination and communication of the research data

Public and non-confidential data. Non-confidential data is used for the preparation of public publications, printed materials, promotional materials, etc., which are distributed and communicated to specific stakeholders or the general public.

All publications are published in accordance with the 5G-TIMBER Data Management Plan and are shared through open research repositories: Zenodo [12] and Open Research Europe [13].

Zenodo is a general-purpose open access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE [14] program that allows researchers to store research papers, datasets, research software, reports and other research-related digital artefacts.

A permanent Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is minted for each submission, making recorded items easy to cite.

Like Zenodo, Open Research Europe is an open access repository that allows researchers to publish any research they want to share, supporting reproducibility, transparency and impact. It uses an open research publication model for publication within days of submission, followed by open professional peer review. Includes references to all supporting data and materials, allowing for re-analysis, replication and reuse.

Both Green and Gold open access publications and the underlying data must be deposited in the above-mentioned open access repositories.

A machine-readable electronic copy (e.g., accepted author's manuscript or the final PDF if allowed by the publisher) must be deposited in the repository as soon as possible, but no later than upon publication. For green open access, authors should include a link to the final version and the accepted author manuscript (AAM) should be used for deposit. This is the final peer-reviewed version of the manuscript, including the reviewers' comments, but without the publisher's design.

All public results, after review and approval by the 5G-TIMBER Management Body, will be shared publicly via the 5G-TIMBER website and open research data repositories.

All publications are published in accordance with the 5G-TIMBER project's Data Management Plan and the project's intellectual property management strategy described below, thus ensuring the protection of the project's intellectual property, personal data, other data and information.

6.3 Intellectual property protection and exploitation of the research data and results

During the regular project meetings, the 5G-TIMBER project partners discuss the potential of the project results that may lead to commercial use and therefore decide to protect the data.

This is monitored by the WP8 representative and appropriate measures are taken to protect such results for the purpose of use when incidents occur. Such results are not shared publicly. Instead, the data is archived in a secure internal storage and the corresponding deliverable is shared with the European Commission only during the regular project review process.

6.4 Data Generation and Collection

All data and information collected during the 5G-TIMBER project activities will be analysed, refined and organized into a consolidated data set, which will be stored in a secure data repository accessible to all project partners.

To track collected data, each work group leader is responsible for defining and describing all collected data sets specific to their individual work package. This shall be done by completing the dataset information table, which will be saved in Microsoft Teams.

It is the responsibility of the WP leaders to update the dataset information table every 3 months (after cooperation with their work program partners) during the life of the 5G-TIMBER project.

The first update of the 5G-TIMBER dataset information table is done during the first 8 months of the project.

At the time of compiling this result, the project was only 4 months old and much of the data has not yet been compiled. Work package leaders have prepared preliminary dataset information table based on the datasets expected in their work packages.

6.5 Data archiving and storage

The project partners coordinate the details of datasets storage before processing the data. Datasets related to the project management are stored in a MS Teams file repository. It is the project's file repository and online collaboration platform throughout the life of the 5G-TIMBER project; and up to 10 years after the end of the project for final closure activities – after which the data is permanently deleted.

The internal structure of the different WP folders is determined by the work package leader.

The project partner generating the data is responsible for uploading their datasets to the team's repository.

The respective team leader is responsible for periodically reviewing the team folders and ensuring that project data sets are archived properly and in accordance with the Data Management Plan procedures.

At the end of the project, the final datasets, public releases and publications will be transferred to the Zenodo and Open Research Europe repositories, which ensures the sustainable archiving of the final research data.

Items stored in these repositories are preserved throughout their lifetime.

Zenodo currently has the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN and has a defined experimental program for at least the next 20 years (based on Zenodo's general policy [15]).

6.6 FAIR data management

FAIR's data management is related to the European Commission's guidelines on findability, accessibility, interoperability and reuse of data.

5G-TIMBER links FAIR data management to naming conventions, contributions to open data research, data identification and retrieval, and metadata provisions and data reusability.

The aim of the 5G-TIMBER project is to maximize access to and reuse of research data generated during the project.

At the same time, the 5G-TIMBER project has created data sets or parts of data sets that cannot be shared in order to protect the exploitable results, business secrets and the privacy of the participants.

6.7 Data findability

5G-TIMBER uses the Zenodo and Open Research Europe repositories as the main tools to make the research data of the project findable according to the Horizon Europe open access mandate.

The Horizon Europe 5G-TIMBER community will be created on both the Zenodo and Open Research Europe websites, and all public datasets and results and scientific publications will be uploaded to this community during the project.

In addition, all project uploads are linked to the European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) community to ensure maximum findability. More information on making data available through Zenodo follows.

All uploads are enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including grant number and project acronym.

Zenodo provides version control and assigns a DOI to all uploaded items.

The consortium uses metadata to describe data collection and facilitate data retrieval and reuse. In general, metadata has a dual nature: descriptive, thus providing information on how to find and identify data (titles, author, keywords), and administrative insight into when and how the data was created, file type and other technical information, and who can access it.

By default, the metadata associated with each dataset published by Zenodo is:

1. Identifiers of digital objects;
2. Version numbers;
3. Bibliographic information;
4. Keywords;
5. Abstract/Description;
6. Related project and community;
7. Related publications and reports;
8. Grant information;
9. Access and license information;
10. Language.

Each partner is responsible for uploading the public datasets they create and assigning appropriate keywords to these datasets. Dataset-specific keywords must describe the content of the dataset.

In addition, a set of general keywords that should apply to all public datasets, scientific publications, and public publications.

As part of the 5G-TIMBER quality plan and control, a series of document/report templates have been created to ensure a consistent approach to all 5G-TIMBER data and its versions.

Zenodo supports DOI versioning [16], which allows users to update datasets after they are published and allows researchers to easily cite either specific versions of a record or cite all versions of a record via a top-level DOI. DOI

stands for "Digital Object Identifier", which means "digital identifier of an object". As described in the DOI manual [17]:

1. The DOI syntax consists of a DOI prefix and a DOI suffix separated by a forward slash. The DOI prefix consists of the directory indicator followed by the registrant's code. The directory indicator is always "10". The registrant code is a unique string assigned to a registrant e.g. 1001. The directory indicator and the registrant code are separated by a dot ".".
2. The DOI suffix consists of a character string of any length chosen by the registrant. Each suffix shall be unique to the prefix element that precedes it. The unique suffix can be a sequential number, or it might incorporate an identifier generated from or based on another system used by the registrant (e.g. ISAN, ISBN, ISRC, ISSN, ISTC, etc.)

Zenodo registers one DOI per version of the dataset, and in addition one Concept DOI is registered.

The Concept DOI represents all versions of a record, and semantically link all the per-version DOIs.

As an example, DOI versioning of a dataset that is released in several versions can look like this:

1. v1.0: 10.1001/zenodo.123
2. v2.0: 10.1001/zenodo.321
3. Concept (all versions): 10.1001/zenodo.122

The first two DOIs for versions v1.0 and v.2.0 represent the specific versions of the dataset, while the Concept (the last DOI) represents all the versions of the dataset package, i.e. the concept of the dataset and the ensemble of versions.

They are referred to as Version DOIs and Concept DOIs, but in fact they are both normal DOIs.

This does not, however, mean that a new DOI will be assigned each time the metadata of the dataset is edited (e.g. change the title of a file or dataset). A new DOI version will only be created if one updates the actual files that have been uploaded.

The aim of the Horizon Europe open access mandate is to make research data generated by Horizon Europe projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, while also accepting the protection of personal or sensitive data due to privacy concerns and/or commercial or security reasons.

All public datasets, scientific publications and deliverables are uploaded to Zenodo and made publicly available for free.

Publications and underlying datasets are linked using persistent identifiers (DOI versions).

Datasets and publications that are "confidential" are not shared due to privacy concerns or potential for commercial use.

If such cases occur during the project, they will be notified in the final version of the Data Management Plan.

Metadata, including licenses for individual data records and record collections, can be collected by record identifier and full name using the OAI-PMH protocol.

Metadata is also discoverable via the public REST-API.

The data is available through Zenodo and thus accessible through any web browsing application.

The list of expected datasets presented in Chapter 6 constitutes the first version of the dataset description; it will evolve and grow as the 5G-TIMBER project evolves.

In addition, some information about the datasets, such as the size of the datasets, remains unknown at this time. An updated version of this list will be provided at the end of the 5G-TIMBER project.

6.8 Data accessibility

This initial Data Management Plan is adapted and serves the 5G-TIMBER objectives of providing data for an open research pilot.

Data sets that are shared are checked to ensure that:

1. They are not confidential, and do not contain personal or sensitive business information.
2. Permission has been obtained from relevant stakeholders and/ or data subjects. Data sharing does not compromise exploitation or prospects for intellectual property protection consistent with innovation, intellectual property rights and data management processes.

Accordingly, datasets will be reviewed by the 5G-TIMBER members in collaboration with the Project Coordinator, each partner's Designated Data Protection Officer and data owners and must be approved before they can apply to contribute to the open research pilot.

These parties and the initiating consortium partner(s) then agree on licensing (such as creative commons or public domain).

Following approval in principle, 5G-TIMBER will make the datasets accessible through appropriate open access repositories following the guidelines of the grant agreement.

Confirmation of the availability of the open approach to the data must be sent by e-mail from the actual owners of the data to the project coordinator. For this purpose, the confirmation email sent to the project coordinator must include the consent that the data may be distributed outside the consortium.

The following information should be included:

1. Owner of the data;
2. Description of the data (what the data include);
3. Data file names and version;
4. Consent to publish the data outside the 5G-TIMBER consortium.

The following repository systems will be used in the 5G-TIMBER project:

1. **MS Teams.** MS Teams is the 5G-TIMBER project's main file repository and documentation/ data exchange between consortium partners.

MS Teams also serves as a centralized access to relevant information and important documents to track project progress and promote communication between partners, document review and repository.

MS Teams is the main server where all project data is shared and exchanged between different beneficiaries.

2. **Zenodo & Open Research Europe.** All research publications, including public deliverables and public parts of underlying datasets, will be uploaded to the Horizon Europe 5G-TIMBER community in addition to Zenodo's European Commission-funded research (OpenAIRE) community.

Zenodo is a comprehensive open research data repository that collects research data from all disciplines.

Open Research Europe allows researchers to publish any research they want to share, supporting reproducibility, transparency and impact.

Uses an open research publication model: publication within days of submission followed by open professional peer review.

Includes citations to all supporting data and materials, allowing for reanalysis, reproduction, and reuse.

6.9 Data interoperability

Data interoperability is mainly considered for 5G-TIMBER's internal purposes. Data interoperability includes data reuse, exchange and general use.

To ensure data interoperability outside the consortium, 5G-TIMBER will follow intellectual property rules.

As for file naming conventions to maximize data interoperability, the consortium does its best to follow common file names such as .XML, .XLS(X), etc.

In addition to the commonly used standards mentioned above (in terms of commonly used file names), 5G-TIMBER is exploring the possibility of following other internationally recognized standards for both the actual data and the software being produced.

The goal of the 5G-TIMBER project is to collect and document data in a standardized way so that datasets can be easily understood, reused and compiled between different parties interested in using them. Standard technical terminology is also used to facilitate interdisciplinary interoperability.

6.10 Data Reusability

The data in the concept of the 5G-TIMBER project are treated as both pre-existing data and data created during the project.

The data is properly and securely stored on a convenient and secure server to allow easy access outside the consortium, but at the same time to control user access. This is achieved through the 5G-TIMBER XY server.

The data reuse is a key component of FAIR. This ensures that the data can be reused for purposes other than those for which it was originally created.

6.11 Data Management Plan

The Data Management Plan will describe the procedures that will be followed throughout the 5G-TIMBER project. It is important to consider carefully and document the ways of collecting and processing data.

Specifically, it is important to specify:

1. who is responsible for the data?
2. who has access to the project data?
3. what will happen to the data after the closure of the project?

The principles that will be included in the procedures set out in the 5G-TIMBER Data Management Plan are listed below.

1. Data acquiring, including:

- 1.1 Self-collecting;
- 1.2 Re-using previously collected data;
- 1.3 Public (Open) Data collecting;
- 1.4 Re-using data collected by others;
- 1.5 Buying data.

2. Data description, including:

- 2.1 Data types;
- 2.2 Data integration;
- 2.3 Data preservation;
- 2.4 Data permissions.

3. Data formats, including:

- 3.1 Data formats choice explaining;
- 3.2. Using open formats;
- 3.3 Using standard formats;
- 3.4 Using Machine-readable formats;
- 3.5 Recommended data formats.

4. Data volume, including estimating the data volume at the end of the project: preservation, access, backup, data exchange, hardware and software, technical support, expenses.

5. Data creation and collection methods and procedures, including:

- 5.1 Naming the existing standard procedures and methods;
- 5.2 Available data standards;
- 5.3 Ensuring data quality (availability, integrity, confidentiality);
- 5.4 Errors handling (input errors, problematic values).

6. Software.

7. Organisation of Data:

- 7.1 Systematisation;
- 7.2 Folder and file organisation;

7.3 Cloud-based code repository;

7.4 Metadata.

6.11.1 Data Lifecycle

The 5G-TIMBER project takes into account the different stages where data is created, managed or used throughout the project lifecycle.

The stages of the data lifecycle are as follows:

1. Data Creation and Collection;
2. Data Processing and Analysis;
3. Data Publication and Utilization;
4. Data Storage, Archiving and Reuse.

- 1. Data creation and collection** is the stage that involves the creation and/ or collection of data based on project activities and various experimental data, project reports and other documents or spreadsheets. This includes the creation of data by the respective owner and its collection in a structured format and layout that allows it to be processed by other project components and/ or partners.
- 2. Data processing and analysis** is the stage related to the actual data processing by the various data processors. The data processors are the project partners who have access to the data based on project needs and expected outcomes. At this stage, it is necessary to ensure that the processors can carry out the data processing in a concise manner to meet the needs of the 5G-TIMBER project, including the verification, organization, transformation, integration and extraction of the data for the intended purpose. Data analysis includes all operations performed on real data and a methodology that describes existing facts, identifies restrictions, develops data refinements, etc.
- 3. Data publication and utilization** is the stage that involves data publication, which means the need to share data openly with the public. In addition, the use includes steps towards data sharing within the consortium of projects. Control mechanisms must be in place to ensure data is shared with appropriate protection of proprietary data and data integrity.
- 4. Data storage, archiving and reuse** stage is critical as it relates to data access, storage and sharing. This includes actions to prevent accidental data loss or deletion, data corruption and/or unauthorized access to data. Data storage and archiving are also strongly related to data reusability, which is also part of FAIR's data processing.

Each of the above stages sets out specific metrics to be followed in relation to data management along with controls. These stages and metrics are summarized in the data management report template ([Appendix IX](#)Data Management Report Template) is used to check data management compliance at different stages of the project.

6.11.2 Data Protection Impact Assessment

Taking into account article 35 of the GDPR, each partner shall evaluate if the personal data processing is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals, taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the type of processing.

In this case, the partner shall conduct a data protection impact assessment well before the collection/ processing will take place and report its results to the project Ethics Panel to be included in deliverable D7.8

The GDPR Article 35 states that a DPIA is necessary where an organisation, processes personal data in way that is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of an individual.

GDPR Article 35(3) states that DPIAs are mandatory in a number of processing scenarios where an organization performs automated decision-making based on personal data profiling, large scale processing of special categories of data or systematic monitoring of publicly accessible areas on a large scale.

In particular, a DPIA is required where an organisation:

1. Uses systematic and extensive profiling with significant effects; or
2. Processes special category or criminal offence data on a large scale; or
3. Systematically monitors publicly accessible places on a large scale.

6.11.3 Data Encryption and procedures

Security of Personal Data. According to General Data Protection Regulation Article 32 – the project team shall implement appropriate organisational and technical measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risks, including the encryption of personal data.

Appropriate software solutions suitable for all project participants are used to encrypt the data.

This appropriate technical solution for data encryption will be decided by the project members, taking into account the recommendations of information security experts.

6.11.4 Data Breach and procedures

In case of data breach, the GDPR states that disclosure within 72 hours must be made to the local Data Protection Authority, enabling individuals to be informed and take appropriate remedial action, while in case of organisations' non-compliance with the GDPR provisions, substantial financial recourse will be made against them.

Procedures and requirements are following:

1. The project participant shall immediately notify the data breach to the Data Protection Officer of his/her institution and project.
2. The Data Protection Officer shall notify the data breach to the data protection supervisory authority within 72 hours.
3. The Data Protection Officer shall immediately take appropriate measures to remedy the data breach and to establish the circumstances of the incident.
4. The Data Protection Officer shall, if necessary, contact the data subjects whose personal data are affected by the data breach.

6.11.5 Data Retention Time and procedures

Personal data generated or managed by the project shall be destroyed as soon as possible after the specific objectives to which the data relates are achieved.

Data will be retained for as long as necessary and in no case longer than 3 years after project completion.

If a project member considers that certain data need to be retained for more than 3 years after the end of the project, he/ she shall coordinate this with the Data Protection Officer.

The data shall be stored in a secure environment. The appropriate environment to data storage be decided by the project members in consultation with the Data Protection Officer.

6.11.5.1 Data Deletion and procedures

The data shall be deleted as soon as possible after the need to use the data has ceased. The data will be deleted securely by overwriting the data using special software. The deletion of the data and the appropriate software will be decided by the project members in consultation with the Data Protection Officer.

6.11.6 Project Data, including Research Information and Business/ Trade Secret Confidentiality

Given the potentially confidential nature of data to be exchanged, data should only be made available on a strict *need-to-know* basis, and it should be appropriately secured against access or use by unauthorised parties. Moreover, there might be some specific cases where confidential information generated or managed by the project (e.g. data related to non-public deliverables) might need to be disclosed to specific persons/ entities for specific purposes.

This is the case for instance of the external members that will convey valuable feedback about the project activities. Those cases shall be approved by the whole project consortium and a non-disclosure agreement will be requested to ensure that the external people/entity doesn't use the information without the project approval.

6.11.7 Roles and responsibilities

In order to ensure compliance with data management decisions related to the Data Management Plan, the following measures apply in 5G-TIMBER:

1. WP leaders are responsible for the data processing in their respective WPs.
2. Each partner has appointed a dedicated Data Privacy Single Point of Contact/ Data Protection Officer for 5G-TIMBER.
3. Each partner's project manager and Data Privacy Single Point of Contact/ Data Protection Officer should ensure that project personnel are familiar with the Data Management Plan and implement all principles described in the 5G-TIMBER Data Management Plan.
4. Data owners have ultimate responsibility for the specifics of the 5G-TIMBER Data Management Plan.

5. For the general activities of the 5G-TIMBER project, the project coordinator (TalTech) is considered the Data Protection Officer of 5G-TIMBER.

7. Conclusions and Next Actions

This deliverable D7.7 “Data and ethics management plan” has described the work performed in WP7, Task 7.3 “Data Management, Ethics and Ethical Compliance”. This includes the identification of the main references (i.e. international data management and ethics standards, international and national legislations and codes regarding the data management, ethics and legal concerns) that lay the foundation for the 5G-TIMBER data management, ethics and legal background framework.

The Background framework is constantly evolving and requires to be continuously monitored for ensuring the compliance of project activities with respect to current EU legal framework and research ethics concerns.

Based on the description of the use cases (still under development during the editing of this document), this deliverable foresees the potential data management, ethics and legal concerns.

By adopting a “concerns and safeguards” approach to foresee and address ethics issues, the document proceeded in the definition of the code of conduct, the 5G-TIMBER Research Ethics Protocol, to be respected during the whole project lifecycle, including the definition of Ethics Panel and its role, individuals recruitment rules, safeguards for ensuring privacy and personal data protection (i.e. information sheets and consent procedures), as well as for ensuring project data confidentiality (i.e. non-disclosure agreements).

In case of needs, the Research Ethics Protocol will be accordingly revised and enhanced with the objective of ensuring the observance and promotion of good research practices and the principles that underpin them.

The next version of this document D7.8 “Initial data management report” will be delivered at month 12.

The final version of this document D7.9 “Final data management report” will be delivered at month 36.

Finally, this deliverable provided the 5G-TIMBER consortium with templates for information sheet, consent form and non-disclosure agreement for external members.

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9. Appendix I: Human participation related activities

Table 8 summarizes the activities that are foreseen to involve human participation in the 5G-TIMBER project activities.

Table 8. Human participation related activities per relevant tasks

Task	Description	Target audience
T2.4: AI-driven edge computing and precise indoor localization	UC2.1 might potentially make use of image/video based localization technique for tracking workers for monitoring their safety	Employees (workers, technicians, engineers) of Harmet factory
T3.3: Augmented reality supported manufacturing and machine servicing system setup	Performing lab trials of AR solutions for machine servicing using AR glasses or handheld devices. Performing field trials of AR device positioning for the assembly operations.	For lab trials: TBC For field trials: Employees (workers, technicians, engineers) of Harmet factory
T4.2: Field trials for sawmill machinery production and operations UCs	Performing trials of using AR tools for machine assembly and servicing support; trials of using IoT, edge image processing for fault detection and prediction, trials of machines remote servicing and operation using 5G communication.	Employees (workers, technicians, engineers) of the sawmills
T4.3: Field trials for wooden houses UCs	Trials of using IoT devices-based material based monitoring and modelling for material quality control and use process optimization; Trials of using 5G for high precision indoor positioning for logistics and process optimization purposes; Trials of using 5G and image processing for workers safety; Trials of using AR, activity tracing over 5G communication for assembly process efficiency improvement purposes; Trials of using	Employees (workers, technicians, engineers) of the wooden house construction companies

	<p>raw material models and structural health monitoring feedback for product quality improvements and process optimization.</p>	
<p>T4.4: Field trials of wood-based construction, renovation and waste valorisation</p>	<p>Pilots will be conducted in three countries, precise timing and locations were decided in WP3. Trials of using AR and BIM models over 5G for assembly efficiency improvements on construction site. Trials of using image processing and 5G positioning for human safety and wellness on construction sites Material properties driven biochemical valorisation of composite wood waste - piloting materials chemical properties driven waste sorting to enable biochemical recycling supported by materials information (Lead VTT). Due to complexity of the use case each construction site will run a single pilot.</p>	<p>Employees (workers, technicians, engineers) of the wooden house construction companies, renovation companies, and waste valorisation partner.</p>

10. Appendix II: Health and safety regulations in 5G-TIMBER

5G-TIMBER confirms that, during its evaluation and demonstration activities, will conform with all the appropriate Health and Safety (H&S) procedures on departmental/institutional/regional/national level both for entities' staff as well as with regard to external participants.

The overview of the respective regulations for the 5G-TIMBER test sites is provided in the following Table 9.

Table 9. Health and Safety (H&S) regulations in 5G-TIMBER

5G-TIMBER Test site	Partner	H&S Local/national/institutional guidelines/regulation/standard [Name/Title]	H&S protocol description (brief)	Application level (Departmental/ Institutional/ Regional/ National)	Documentation (link/document)	Relevant to staff/ external users /both
Testbeds of TalTech (Tallinn, Estonia)	TalTech	TalTech Occupational Health and Safety Management Regulations	The directive is issued based on clause 9) of § 11 of TalTech Statutes.	Institutional	https://upload.ttu.ee/show/file/4UQS54:6ac1676c133547e0d6b5293065c2d2c4.pdf	Both

<p>Woodhouse manufacturing site (Harmet, Puusepa tee 4, Kumna, 76614 Harjuma, Estonia)</p> <p>“Pilot A: tailored made construction of wood house in Norway” (exact location TBD, Norway”</p>	<p>Harmet</p>	<p>Harmet OÜ Management System Manual</p> <p>Visiting rules of the Harmet Kumna factory</p>	<p>Procedure 2.13 "Occupational Health and Safety"</p>	<p>Institutional</p>	<p>Attachment files</p>	<p>Both</p>
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The project partners will specify their Health and Safety regulations in 5G-TIMBER.

11. Appendix III: Ethics Checklist Form

This form must be filled out by the respective Ethics Panel member of the partner leading the testing/ use case.

Ethics Checklist Form	Please circle as necessary	
<i>I General Information</i>		
1. Ethics Panel (EP) member responsible for this project: [Name, email address]		
2. Partners involved in the testing (also indicate leading partner):		
3. Title of the testing/use case:		
4. Purpose of this research study (briefly explain):		
<i>II Participants and Informed consent</i>		
5. Have human participants and their involvement been clearly described in the Ethics Controlling Report? (if no, please explain)	Yes	No
6. Are recruitment criteria, information sheets and informed consent procedures for this research study/testing in accordance with the Ethics policy/protocols described herein, available and accessible in the appropriate locations? (if no, please explain)	Yes	No
7. Does the principal investigator demonstrate good awareness of the informed consent procedures and related documents? (if no, please explain)	Yes	No
8. In case the testing includes participation incentives in forms other than the expected benefit from the research outcomes, are these in accordance with the ethics principles as described in D7.7?	Yes	No

9. Will participants receive adequate feedback at the completion of the study, including a debriefing if that is necessary?	Yes	No
10. Have gender balance considerations been taken into account by the principal investigator?	Yes	No
<u>III Ethics control instruments</u>		
11. Is there a need for ethical approval by a relevant body?	Yes	No
a. If yes, has it been approved?	Yes	No
i. If yes, has it been uploaded to the collaboration platform in folder WP7/T7.4?	Yes	No
12. Does the principal investigator shows good awareness of ethics controls and procedures/documents? (if no, please explain; also inform and instruct accordingly the principal investigator; inform the Ethics Panel by writing when this procedure is completed and the principal investigator shows appropriate awareness)	Yes	No
<u>IV Privacy</u>		
13. Are all the privacy protection related documents (DMP; DPIA-if necessary; information sheets and informed consent forms and Data Processing Agreements) available, appropriate with the responsible persons (DPO, Data Processors and Data Controllers) designated for each relevant participating partner? (if no, please explain; also inform and instruct accordingly the principal investigator; inform the Ethics Panel by writing when this procedure is completed and all documents are available and accessible).	Yes	No
14. Does the principal investigator shows good awareness of procedures/guidelines/legislation for protecting privacy? (if no, please explain; also inform and instruct accordingly the principal investigator; inform the Ethics Panel by writing when this procedure is completed and	Yes	No

the principal investigator shows appropriate awareness)		
15. Is all of the following information (questions 16-20) clearly documented, available and accessible to the Ethics Panel Members and appropriate for the testing/use case to be performed?	Yes (All)	No
16. Appropriate actions for the investigators do to make sure that the information collected on persons will not get in wrong hands?	Yes	No
17. Appropriate actions that a person can do if he/she wants to find out more about the study, or to complain about the way he/she was treated?	Yes	No
18. Appropriate agreements to ensure that personal information may be shared with any other partner of third party (if applicable)? (If no, please explain)	Yes	No
19. Information in relation to what will happen to any information (including photos, video or voice recordings) given by a person, what are the person's rights, how and how long will it be stored? (If no, please explain)	Yes	No
20. Is 5G-TIMBER Data Protection Policy regarded?	Yes	No
<u>V Health and Safety (H&S)</u>		
21. In case the research poses risks of physical or psychological harm to participants by using deception, obtaining sensitive information or exposing them for risks in terms of safety and/or security/confidentiality hazards, are appropriate and adequate safety measures and procedures taken and considered by the principal investigator? (If no, please explain)	Yes	No
22. Is the principal investigator aware of the H&S procedures of the testing/research? (if no, please explain; also inform and instruct accordingly the principal	Yes	No

investigator; inform the Ethics Panel by writing when this procedure is completed and the principal investigator shows appropriate awareness)		
<u>VI Risk Management</u>		
23. In case risks exist, does the research adequately manage these risks by including appropriate relevant risk assessments, procedures, and mitigation measures? (if no, please explain)	Yes	No
24. Is there health insurance coverage for persons participating in the testing/ experiments? (if no, please explain)	Yes	No
25. Have I as part of the project informed the Ethics Panel in writing about the ethical issues I have identified and of which I am aware?	Yes	No

12. Appendix IV: Ethics Controlling Report

This questionnaire on ethical and legal issues will be filled in by the investigator responsible for conducting trials involving human participants (i.e. **consortium partner leading the testing activity**).

The aim is to remind the researcher to consider all relevant ethical aspects before planning and conducting the activity and/or any data collection activities within 5G-TIMBER.

The questionnaire is divided into six subsections: General Information, Participants and Informed consent, Ethics control instruments, Privacy, Safety and Risk Management.

Questionnaire on Ethical and Legal issues

I General information

1. Name and affiliation (i.e. partner) of the person filling out the report:

2. Brief summary of the activity/testing (including type of involvement of human participants]:

Have I obtained approval from my institution's ethics committee and /or other relevant responsible body/authority for the planned testing activities involving human participants?

Yes No

If **yes**, please state by whom:

If **no**, please explain why:

II Participants and informed consent

3. Are you aware of the informed consent procedures that relate to your testing?

Yes No

If **yes**, briefly provide the link to the relevant documents:

4. Do you intend to conduct testing/pilots with individuals who might not understand the informed consent form?

Yes No

If **yes**, briefly explain the procedures you follow in order to obtain informed consent:

If **no**, please continue with the next question.

5. Is there any doubt about the individual's cognitive capacity to consent?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please clarify who will provide consent in such instance:

If **no** please continue with the next question.

6. a) Is the informed consent provided in common language to be understood by a lay person?

Yes No

If **no**, why not? Please provide an example of any technical terminology (*termini technici*) used within the description.

b) Will the participant be given sufficient time to reflect his/her decision of giving or withholding consent?

Yes No

If **no**, why not? Please indicate the time given to the participant.

7. Is the participant unable to consent for any reason not specifically listed in questions 2 to 4?

Yes No

If **yes**, no experiment will be performed since these participants are excluded from 5G-TIMBER trials.

If **no**, please continue with the next question.

8. Is the participant for any reason unable to read the form by him-/herself?

q Yes q No

If **yes**, please continue with b)

If **no**, please continue with the next question.

b) There are a range of people who are unable to read the consent form; these include those who may also have severe visual impairments (e.g. cataract, glaucoma).

9. Have gender balance considerations been taken into account as per the provisions of D7.7 – Legal framework, ethics & gender balance?

q Yes q No

In **either case**, please briefly explain how and provide relevant information for male/female research participants (how many, type of involvement):

10. Does your experiment include vulnerable participants?

a) in terms of exposure-related vulnerability (e.g. pedestrians, bicyclists, motorcyclists) ?

q Yes q No

If **Yes**, please provide details (number, type of involvement):

b) in terms of non-exposure related disability (e.g. elderly persons, persons with disabilities or other cognitive impairments / learning difficulties)?

q Yes q No

If **Yes**, please provide details (number, type of disability, type of involvement):

11. Are any illiterate foreseen participants?

q Yes q No

If **no**, please continue with the question 10.

If **yes**, be advised that an illiterate participant has to provide oral consent which has to be witnessed at least by one person. If that is the case, please name the prospective witness:

Additionally, please answer the following question.

12. Will the oral consent of an illiterate participant that is witnessed be in accordance with your national legislation?

q Yes q No

13. Is there an international or national legislation, which you must follow *in relation to the type of testing* you will be within the 5G-TIMBER project involving:

a) human participants in general?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (reference number and short description of procedure):

b) participants with cognitive impairments / learning difficulties or other disabilities?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (reference number and short description of procedure):

c) *illiterate* participants?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details (reference number and short description of procedure):

14. Are there participation incentives other than the expected benefits from the research outcomes that are provided to participants?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide details.

15. Will participants receive adequate feedback at the completion of the study, including a debriefing if that is necessary?

Yes No

In *either case*, please briefly provide details.

III Ethics control instruments

16. At which level of your organization / enterprise, *ethics controls* are audited?

laboratory or workgroup

division or department

institution

local/regional

q national

17. Is there an ethics controlling body in your region / country from which you must obtain ethics opinion/permission, other than those that are responsible within the 5G-TIMBER consortium?

q Yes q No

If **Yes**, please provide details about the body relevant for you and the procedure that has to be adhered to in order to obtain ethical approval of experiments:

18. Is there an established ethics control procedure which you must follow before performing tests with:

a) human participants in general?

q Yes q No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief description.

b) human participants with cognitive impairments / learning difficulties or other disabilities?

q Yes q No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief description.

c) *illiterate* participants?

q Yes q No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief description.

IV *Privacy*

19. Is personal/private information recorded?

q Yes q No

20. Is there an established Data Protection Authority issuing procedures / standards you must follow before performing tests with human participants and their personal / private data?

q Yes q No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain briefly what corrective actions you will take to ensure privacy of personal data of participants:

21. Do you follow written procedures for protecting privacy?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and state any corrective actions you will take:

22. Do you follow or are you aware of any official national or international guidelines on protecting privacy?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline and provide references:

23. Will you clarify to the participants that all data collected in the activities they are participating in will be kept entirely confidential and that their anonymity will be protected in full?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline and provide references:

24. Do you identify persons and their professions who are authorised to have access to the data collected and / or who have access to any data storage devices, both, paper-based and electronically?

Yes No

If **Yes**, please briefly list these persons and their professions.

V *Health and Safety (H&S)*

25. Will your participants follow any specific H&S procedures /protocols /mitigation measures for the purpose of the testing?

Yes No

In **either case**, please provide a brief outline or explanation and provide some references:

26. [Only in case vulnerable participants participate in the testing] Will vulnerable participants be provided with additional H&S procedures/protocols/mitigation measures than those offered to non-disability participants?

q Yes q No

In **either case**, please explain what and / or why:

27. Will you inform the participants about the H&S procedures / protocols / measures that they need to follow/take?

q Yes q No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and the corrective actions you will take:

VI Risk Management

28. Do you have procedures to perform risk-assessment concerning the breach of privacy and / or breach of safety?

q Yes q No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and refer to any corrective actions you will take:

29. Is your organisation insured against risks as a result of breach of privacy and/or health and safety risks?

q Yes q No

If **Yes**, please provide a brief outline of it and state the insurer, if possible:

If **No**, please explain the reasons briefly and state who would cover any insurance-related costs:

30. For conducting research and manage the risk, do you need to involve other organisations (unit, division, department, etc.) which are outside of your direct supervision, the activities of which may influence the

ethics/legal integrity of your research and constitute potential threats for the ethical and legal conduct of the activity you are leading?

Yes No

If Yes, please provide a brief outline of it and describe the measures you plan to take for avoiding or mitigating these risks:

31. Where any risk assessments relevant to the Framework Directive 89/391/EEC (Health and Safety at Work) and its supporting Directives as per the precautionary principle necessary for the testing?

Yes No

If Yes, please provide a brief outline of these, include the location of relevant risk assessments (e.g. supporting document; link) and briefly describe the identified risks and relevant treatment measures you plan to take for these risks:

13. Appendix V: Information sheet example template

5G-TIMBER Draft Information sheet and informed consent form

Information Sheet

[Date]

5G-TIMBER

Introduction: [Briefly state who you are and explain that you are inviting them to participate in the research you are doing. Inform them that they may talk to anyone they feel comfortable talking with about the research and that they can take time to reflect on whether they want to participate or not.

Assure the participant that if they do not understand some of the words or concepts, that you will take time to explain them as you go along and that they can ask questions now or later.

Example: I am X, working for the Y Research Institute. We are doing research on XY, as part the European Union-funded^[1] 5G-TIMBER research project coordinated by TALLINN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY (TalTech), Estonia in partnership with [Insert NAME of your INSTITUTION^[2]].

I am going to give you information and invite you to be part of this research. Before you decide, you can talk to anyone you feel comfortable with about the research.

In case there are some words that you do not understand, please ask me to stop as we go through the information and I will take time to explain.

If you have questions later, you can ask me about or the staff.]

Purpose of research: [Explain in lay terms why we are doing research within the framework of 5G-TIMBER project. Use local and simplified terms. The language used should clarify rather than confuse. There are guides on the internet to help you find substitutes for words which are overly scientific or are professional jargon.

Example: the purpose of this project is to XY. The findings of this questionnaire / survey / interview / workshop / trial / group discussion / other (Specify.....)^[3] will assist the consortium partners to capture and assess and/or validate the effectiveness of the 5G-TIMBER 5G ecosystem through relevant use cases.]

Participant selection: [most applicable for vulnerable populations: State why this participant has been chosen for this research. People often wonder why they have been chosen to participate and may be fearful, confused or concerned.

Example: We are inviting people with mobility disability to participate in the research on testing new automated technologies for understanding how our proposed developments may best contribute in alleviating such impairments.]

Voluntary Participation and right to refuse or withdraw: [Indicate clearly that they can choose to participate or not. Participants with cognitive impairment, if any, will be reminded about their participation being voluntary before moving to the consent form and signing it.

Example: Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary. You are free to leave at any time, change your mind later and stop participating at any time even if you agreed earlier, without any impacts on you or your future participation in the project. You are also free to refuse to answer any questions or provide any information that you do not wish to discuss. You have the right to ask questions and receive understandable answers before making any decision].

Information on the 5G-TIMBER applications and systems to be tested: [provide as much give information about the applications as is appropriate and understandable about the system and applications and explain what it does/means (including illustrations of the applications or real demos, depending on availability; participants with cognitive impairments, if any, will receive information with illustrations (i.e., pictures, examples of functionalities, in simple language with no jargon.). Explain the known experience with these applications/services (mainly for technological implementations already in the market).

Example: The system and applications we are testing in this research are called A, B, X. Many of them have been tested before but now they will be integrated and tested in large field scale conditions as one system. The application (s) ABX is made by C, D, E. We know of no problem or risks related to its/their use. Some participants in the research will not be given this/these application(s) we are testing. Instead, they will be given another/other application(s) XYZ. There is no risk, other than usual traffic risk associated with the use of this/these application(s) and no known problems.]

Procedures and Protocols: [Describe or explain the exact procedures that will be followed on a step-by-step basis, the tests that will be done, data that will be gathered. Participants should know what to expect and what is expected of them. Use active, rather than conditional, language. Write "we will ask you to...." instead of "we would like to ask you to.... An illustration of the system and applications, if available, will help participants understand the process better ".]

Duration: [Include a statement about the time commitments of the research for the participant including both the duration of the research and follow-up, if relevant.

Example: The research takes place over ___ (number of) days in total. During that time, it will be necessary for you to come to the testing facility _____ (number of) days, for ____ (number of) hours each day. We would like to meet with you for a final validation of the results X months after your last testing.]

Risks: [Explain and describe any possible or anticipated risks. Describe the level of care that will be available in the event that harm does occur, who will provide it, and who will pay for it (e.g., traffic-related risks). A risk can be thought of as being the likelihood that harm may occur. Provide enough information about any risks and relevant mitigation/safety measures that the participant can make an informed decision.

Example: By participating in this research it is there will be no more possibility to be at greater risk than you would otherwise be by driving in usual traffic conditions. While the possibility of this happening is very low, you should still be aware of the possibility. We will try to decrease the chances of this event occurring, but if something unexpected happens, we will provide you with_____.]

Benefits (if reimbursement is used; benefits might not be provided): [Mention only those activities that will be actual benefits and not those to which they are entitled regardless of participation. Benefits may be divided into benefits to the individual, benefits to the community in which the individual resides, and benefits to society as a whole as a result of finding an answer to the research question.

Example: Your participation in this research, is likely to help us find the answer to the research question [state] and the research community / society may benefit from the advancements in automated and connected mobility your participation may result to.].

Reimbursements: [State clearly what you will provide the participants with as a result of their participation. There is no encouragement for using incentives. However, it is recommended that reimbursements for expenses incurred as a result of participation in the research be provided. These may include, for example, travel costs and money for wages lost due to time commitment for testing. The amount should be determined within the host country context.

Example: We will give you [amount of money] to pay for your travel to the place of study taken place/follow-ups/parking and we will give you [amount] for lost work time. You will not be given any other money or gifts to take part in this research.].

Confidentiality: [Explain how the research team will maintain the confidentiality of data.

Example: We will not be sharing the identity of those participating in the research and the record of your involvement in the research will be kept confidential and no-one, but the researchers will be able to see it.

Any personal data you provide will be handled according to the legal requirements outlined in the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.

The information sheet and consent form contain the following confirmations from the research participant:

I have been informed that everything I say will be anonymized. The event data will be recorded via [paper notes/electronic notes/voice recorder/camera recorder] and I can request a copy of these records to review if you wish. I understand that I am also allowed to delete or make any changes to these records if I feel the information I provided could be improved or clarified. I understand that information about my personal involvement in the research will be kept in a secure location at TALLINN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY and that my information will be made anonymous when shared with 5G-TIMBER project team. I understand that the data I provide will be [anonymized, pseudonymized] and the record of my participation will be kept in a file separate from the project data. Any information about you will have a number on it instead of your name. Only the principal investigator will know what your number is and we will lock that

information up with a lock and key. It will not be shared with or given to anyone except [name who will have access to the information]. I understand that the data will be kept for 3 year after the 5G-TIMBER project ends, but my personal data will be destroyed when the project ends.

Sharing of the results: [Where it is relevant, your plan for sharing the information with the participants should be provided. If you have a plan and a timeline for the sharing of information, include the details. You should also inform the participant that the research findings will be shared more broadly, for example, through publications and conferences.

Example: Confidential information will not be shared. There will be small meetings with consortium, and these will be announced. After these meetings, we will publish the results in order that other interested people may learn from our research.]

Who to Contact: [Provide the name and contact information of someone who is involved, informed and accessible (a local person who can actually be contacted and of the Coordinator). State how the research has been approved.

Example: This research conforms to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. This procedure has been reviewed and approved by [name of the local IRB and/or the Academic Ethics Committee of TallTech], which is a committee whose task it is to make sure that research is conducted in an ethical and legal manner. If you have any questions, you may ask them now or later, even after the study has started. In case you are looking for additional information/clarifications for the testing/research that has been conducted, feel free to contact TALLINN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY (Project Coordinator: provide [name, address/telephone number/e-mail]) about any queries relating to my data or the project itself.]

[\[1\]](#) Grant agreement number 101058505.

[\[2\]](#) 5G-TIMBER partner conducting the research and innovation activity will amend all highlighted parts.

[\[3\]](#) Strike through options that do not apply.

14. Appendix VI: Informed consent form example template

5G-TIMBER

Lead partners: *[Insert name of person/institution conducting the research activity]*

Participant Identification Number for this project:

Please ü box

I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated <i>[insert date]</i> explaining the above research project and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that my participation is purely voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without there being any negative consequences. In addition, should I not wish to answer any particular question or questions, I am free to decline and can contact Project Coordinator TALLINN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY via telephone at +372 620 20XX.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that my responses and personal data will be kept strictly confidential.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I give permission for members of the project team to have access to my anonymised data. I understand that my name will not be linked with the research materials, and I will not be identified or identifiable in the report or reports that result from the research.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I agree to take part in the above research project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
I received a copy of both the information sheet and the informed consent form.	<input type="checkbox"/>

 Name of Participant
(or legal representative)

Date

Signature

Name of person taking consent Date Signature
*(if different from lead researcher) To be signed and dated in the presence
of the participant*

Lead researcher Date Signature
To be signed and dated in the presence of the participant

Copies:
Once this has been signed by all parties the participant should receive a copy of the signed and dated participant consent form, the letter/pre-written script/information sheet and any other written information provided to the participants. A copy of the signed and dated consent form should be placed in the project's main record (e.g., a site file), which must be kept in a secure location.

15. Appendix VII: Anonymous Informed Consent Template

5G-TIMBER

Information Sheet

5G-TIMBER project is [Add short project description...]

You are invited to join the 5G-TIMBER research project to take part of the 5G-TIMBER field study. Please take whatever time you need to read and understand the following text. The decision to join, or not to join, is up to you. If you agree with the content, sign the consent form hereafter.

The aim of this activity is to [ADD HERE THE DESCRIPTION].

Your participation is voluntary and free-of-charge, and it will take you [ADD HERE THE TIMEFRAME] minutes/hours. If you accept to participate, you will be asked to [ADD HERE DETAILS]. No risks are foreseen for your participation to this activity. [IN CASE OF FORESEEN RISKS, ADD HERE DETAILS].

The project may stop the field study or take you out of the field study at any time they judge it is in your best interest. They may also remove you from the field study for various other reasons. They can do this without your consent. On the other hand, you are free to stop participating at any time without any obligation.

5G-TIMBER will collect information for the purposes of the 5G-TIMBER project. Only information that is necessary to address the central purpose of the research will be recorded, and the data will be anonymised at the point of collection. Such information will be treated as strictly confidential and handled in accordance with the provisions of the "Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU" (2007/C 303/01), "Convention 108 +" of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals and "General Data Protection Regulation" (EU Regulation 2016/679).

The information will be processed for statistical purposes in an aggregated form. The statistical data and the aggregated information may be disseminated in journals, papers, conferences or events. In any case, your name or any information that could identify you or relate to your identity will not be linked with the research materials. If you have any questions about the field study or the project itself, any problems, unexpected physical or psychological discomforts, any injuries, or think that something unusual or

unexpected is happening, you are free to contact Mr./Ms. [ADD HERE THE CONTACT PERSON] at [ADD HERE THE CONTACT DATA – EMAIL – PHONE NUMBER].

After reading the Information sheet and voluntarily deciding to take part of the project activity, participants shall sign the following Informed Consent Form. Since the form contains personal data, it has to be kept secure by the activity organiser.

5G-TIMBER

Informed Consent Form

	Description	YES	NO
1	I [ADD HERE THE PERSON'S NAME and SURNAME] agree to voluntarily participate to the 5G-TIMBER field study.		
2	I have read the Information Sheet and understand what the field study involves.		
3	I understand that if I decide at any time that I no longer wish to take part in this field study, I can notify the researchers involved and withdraw immediately, without any obligation.		
4	I understand that confidentiality and anonymity will be maintained regarding my personal information, and it will not be possible to identify me at any research stage in the project.		
5	I have had the opportunity to have all my questions answered to my satisfaction. I've been informed of the data governance given by the 5G-TIMBER project.		

A copy of the information sheet and this signed consent form will be given to the signee.

Signature _____ of _____ Subject _____ or _____ Representative _____ and date: _____

16. Appendix VIII: Non-Anonymous Informed Consent Template

5G-TIMBER

Information Sheet

5G-TIMBER project is [*Add short project description...*]

You are invited to join the 5G-TIMBER research project to take part of the 5G-TIMBER field study. Please take whatever time you need to read and understand the following text. The decision to join, or not to join, is up to you. If you agree with the content, sign the consent form hereafter.

The aim of this activity is to [ADD HERE THE DESCRIPTION].

Your participation is voluntary and free-of-charge, and it will take you [ADD HERE THE TIMEFRAME] minutes/hours. If you accept to participate, you will be asked to [ADD HERE DETAILS]. No risks are foreseen for your participation to this activity. [IN CASE OF FORESEEN RISKS, ADD HERE DETAILS].

The project may stop the field study or take you out of the field study at any time they judge it is in your best interest. They may also remove you from the field study for various other reasons. They can do this without your consent. On the other hand, you are free to stop participating at any time without any obligation.

5G-TIMBER will collect information for the purposes of the 5G-TIMBER project. Only information that is necessary to address the central purpose of the research will be recorded, and the data will be anonymised at the point of collection. Such information will be treated as strictly confidential and handled in accordance with the provisions of the "Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU" (2007/C 303/01), "Convention 108 +" of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals and "General Data Protection Regulation" (EU Regulation 2016/679).

The information will be processed for statistical purposes in an aggregated form. The statistical data and the aggregated information may be disseminated in journals, papers, conferences or events. In any case, your

name or any information that could identify you or relate to your identity will not be linked with the research materials. If you have any questions about the field study or the project itself, any problems, unexpected physical or psychological discomforts, any injuries, or think that something unusual or unexpected is happening, you are free to contact Mr./Ms. [ADD HERE THE CONTACT PERSON] at [ADD HERE THE CONTACT DATA – EMAIL – PHONE NUMBER].

5G-TIMBER will collect information for the purposes of the 5G-TIMBER project. Only information that is necessary to address the central purpose of the research will be recorded. Your personal data will not be transferred outside the 5G-TIMBER consortium, and, in any case, they will not be transferred outside Europe. Your personal data will be securely stored and retained for as long as necessary and in no case longer than 3 years after project completion, and safely deleted afterwards. All collected information will be handled in accordance with the provisions of the “Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU” (2007/C 303/01), “Convention 108 +” of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals and “General Data Protection Regulation” (EU Regulation 2016/679). More details about 5G-TIMBER privacy policy can be found at the following link [ADD HERE THE LINK TO THE 5G-TIMBER WEBSITE PAGE]. If you have any questions about the field study or the project itself, any problems, unexpected physical or psychological discomforts, any injuries, or think that something unusual or unexpected is happening, you are free to contact Mr./Ms. [ADD HERE THE CONTACT PERSON] at [ADD HERE THE CONTACT DATA – EMAIL – PHONE NUMBER].

After reading the Information sheet and voluntarily deciding to take part of the project activity, participants shall sign the following Informed Consent Form. Since the form contains personal data, it has to be kept secure by the activity organiser.

5G-TIMBER

Informed Consent Form

	Description	YES	NO
1	I [ADD HERE THE PERSON'S NAME and SURNAME] agree to voluntarily participate to the 5G-TIMBER field study.		

2	I have read the Information Sheet and understand what the field study involves.		
3	I understand that if I decide at any time that I no longer wish to take part in this field study, I can notify the researchers involved and withdraw immediately, without any obligation.		
4	I have had the opportunity to have all my questions answered to my satisfaction. I've been informed of the data governance given by the 5G-TIMBER project.		
5	I voluntary consent with the processing of my personal data in accordance with the provisions of the "Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU" (2007/C 303/01), "Convention 108 +" of the Council of Europe for the Protection of Individuals and "General Data Protection Regulation" (EU Regulation 2016/679).		

A copy of the information sheet and this signed consent form will be given to the signee. Signature of Subject or Representative and date:_____

17. Appendix IX: Data Management Report Template

5G-TIMBER

Data Management Report Template

Performance Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values	Compliance
<i>Data Creation</i>			
Format	Compliance with existing standards of data exchange	XLS, XML etc	[Y/N]
Availability and Readability	Whole package of data available, non-corruption, whole percentage collected	100% received 100% accessible	[Y/N]
Fit for Use	Data follow data compliancy for proper processing and review	100% usable by intended beneficiary	[Y/N]
Consistency and Completeness	Data are consistent and complete for the intended purpose	Including 100% of information for the intended purpose	[Y/N]
Relation	Data follow a precise relation to their purpose	100% purpose precision	[Y/N]
<i>Data Processing and Analysis</i>			
Data logic	Data can be and are processed following a concise logic and approach	New and processed data follow precise data logic	[Y/N]
Organization and Utility	Suitable content organization of data under processing	100% organized data	[Y/N]
Validation	Ensuring that the data under processing are correct and relevant	100% validated and relevant data	[Y/N]
Aggregation	Whenever multiple data need to be aggregated ensure that this is done in a concise approach	100% aggregate-able data	[Y/N]

Transformation	Transformation of data to the proper format(s) for processing	Capability of data for transformation (if needed)	[Y/N]
Calibration	Calibration of data for their intended purpose	Data properly calibrated	[Y/N]
<i>Data Publication and Utilization</i>			
Means-independent	Transferring of the data in a means-independent approach	100% means independent transferability	[Y/N]
Security (a)	Data stored in a secure enough server	At least access control provided over a TLS protocol	[Y/N]
<i>Data Storage, Archiving and Re-Use</i>			
Up to date	Ensuring that the stored data are up to date for the specific purpose and no later version exists	100% updated	[Y/N]
Meta Data	Existence of meta data in stored files	Relevant metadata have been included into the archive per data set	[Y/N]
Security (b)	Access control provided	Access control setup	[Y/N]
Security (c)	Project cloud server is considered as safe enough	At least TLS connection protocol	[Y/N]
Bandwidth	Control of server bandwidth	Effective storage server with scalable bandwidth	[Y/N]
Expiration	Properly setting expiration dates for all data after which the data will be deleted	Expiration date noted	[Y/N]